

Cerebellar Cortical Circuitry in Schizophrenia: A Cellular Framework for Predictive Dysfunction and Psychosis

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Abstract

Schizophrenia (SZ) is a neuropsychiatric disorder characterised by progressive alterations across distributed brain networks that emerge across clinical stages from at-risk states to chronic illness. While traditionally centred on cortical and subcortical regions, converging evidence implicates the cerebellum as a critical node in the pathophysiology of SZ in relation to cognitive dysfunction and impaired predictive processing. Advancing this framework requires moving beyond systems-level observation to define the cellular and microcircuit mechanisms underlying cerebellar involvement. Here, we synthesise evidence on cerebellar cellular alterations in SZ, based on a structured analysis of human postmortem studies, neuroimaging findings, and experimental models relevant to SZ pathophysiology. Across principal neuronal populations, including Purkinje cells, granule cells, and inhibitory interneurons, data reveal convergent microstructural and functional abnormalities rather than uniform neuronal loss. Purkinje cells exhibit reduced dendritic complexity, decreased spine density, and altered intrinsic and synaptic properties, indicating impaired integration and output signalling. In parallel, alterations in the granular layer, including disrupted development, synaptic organisation, and NMDA receptor-dependent plasticity, are likely to impair input processing. These changes are accompanied by widespread alterations in GABAergic, glutamatergic, serotonergic, and dopaminergic signalling, leading to disruption of E/I tone across of cerebellum. We hypothesize that the synergistic impairment of cerebellar input transformation and output represents a fundamental substrate in SZ. Within a predictive processing framework, these deficits are hypothesized to derail internal model formation and prediction error signalling, thereby precipitating impairments in cognitive coordination, multisensory integration, and salience processing. This multi-scale synthesis provides a mechanistic scaffold for understanding the cerebellar contribution to the cognitive and perceptual landscape of SZ, while highlighting the imperative for future research to integrate longitudinal, cellular, and computational approaches.

1. Introduction

1.1 Schizophrenia (SZ) as a brain network disorder

Schizophrenia (SZ) is a neuropsychiatric disorder characterised by alterations in distributed brain networks affecting perception, cognition, and behaviour. Current frameworks conceptualise SZ within a clinical staging model that captures its longitudinal progression from at-risk mental states (prodromal) to first-episode psychosis and later chronic stages, reflecting its neurodevelopmental trajectory and dynamic progression (Fusar-Poli, McGorry et al. 2017, Fusar-Poli, Correll et al. 2021). Early clinical stages, including the prodromal and first-episode phases, are critical periods during which pathophysiological processes emerge, and clinical outcomes are shaped (Fusar-Poli, McGorry et al. 2017, Fusar-Poli, Correll et al. 2021). Clinically, SZ is defined by disturbances in reality testing, including hallucinations, delusions, and disorganised thinking (Marder and Cannon 2019, Queirós, Coelho et al. 2019). Beyond observable symptoms, psychosis involves profound alterations in subjective experience, including disturbances of self, salience attribution, and sense of reality (Fusar-Poli, Estradé et al. 2022). These features contribute to a substantial and increasing global burden, with persistent disability and reduced life expectancy (Solmi, Seitidis et al. 2023).

Current approaches to early detection rely on the identification of at-risk mental states and the prodromal phase of psychosis, characterised by subtle cognitive, perceptual, and behavioural alterations (Yung and McGorry 1996, Schultze-Lutter, Michel et al. 2015). Clinical high-risk (CHR-P) criteria combine attenuated psychotic symptoms, genetic vulnerability, and functional decline. However, these criteria remain heterogeneous and show limited prognostic precision, with only a subset of individuals transitioning to psychosis (Fusar-Poli, Bechdolf et al. 2013, Salazar de Pablo, Radua et al. 2021).

Earlier work introduced the concept of “basic symptoms”, referring to subjective disturbances in cognition and perception that precede overt psychosis and reflect early neurobiological alterations (Schultze-Lutter 2009). Despite these advances, current risk definitions lack biological specificity. Large-scale umbrella reviews indicate that available biomarkers show limited consistency and clinical utility across studies (Fuentes-Claramonte, Estradé et al. 2024). Normative modelling approaches further demonstrate that most individuals at CHR-P exhibit neuroanatomical measures within the range of healthy variability, indicating that macroscale brain alterations alone are insufficient to explain psychosis risk (Haas, Ge et al. 2024). *These findings highlight the need to investigate cellular and microcircuit mechanisms underlying circuit dysfunction.*

Symptoms typically emerge in adolescence or early adulthood, and only 50% of the patients are responsive to existing therapies, with a life expectancy 15–20 years shorter than for healthy individuals (Correll, Solmi et al. 2022). Although existing therapies can effectively address positive symptoms, they often fall short of alleviating negative and cognitive symptoms and are associated with considerable neurological and metabolic side effects (Stepnicki, Kondej et al. 2018, Robbins 2019).

Negative symptoms, including avolition, anhedonia, and social withdrawal, represent a major and treatment-resistant dimension of SZ, with recent large-scale meta-analytic evidence indicating limited and heterogeneous efficacy across pharmacological, psychosocial, and neuromodulatory interventions (Damiani, Stefanelli et al. 2026). Cognitive dysfunction represents a core and persistent feature of SZ and a major determinant of functional outcome. Deficits in executive function, working memory, attention, and processing speed emerge early, often preceding full clinical expression, and persist across disease stages (Marder and Cannon 2019, Catalan, Salazar de Pablo et al. 2021, Salazar de Pablo, Radua et al. 2021, McCutcheon, Keefe et al. 2023). Recent evidence indicates that cognitive disturbances at the CHR stage define a biologically grounded pathway to SZ, characterised by brain signatures that resemble those observed in established disease and involve distributed cortical and cerebellar regions (Koutsouleris, Vetter et al. 2026). These findings support the notion that cognitive impairment reflects alterations in large-scale brain systems rather than isolated regional deficits.

SZ arises from the interaction of genetic liability and environmental exposures acting during critical periods of brain development (Jones 2013, Crossley, Zugman et al. 2020, King, Mothersill et al. 2023, Owen, Legge et al. 2023). These factors converge on synaptic development, neuronal connectivity, and circuit maturation, leading to persistent alterations in brain function. Neuroimaging and genetic studies consistently demonstrate structural and functional abnormalities across prefrontal, temporal, thalamic, and subcortical regions (Wright, Rabe-Hesketh et al. 2000, Cannon, van Erp et al. 2003, McCutcheon, Reis Marques et al. 2020). These findings are formalised in the disconnection hypothesis, which posits that SZ reflects impaired integration across distributed brain systems rather than focal pathology (Friston, Brown et al. 2016).

Within large-scale brain networks, the cerebellum has emerged as a key node contributing to higher-order cognitive processes. Through extensive connections with prefrontal, parietal, and limbic regions, the cerebellum supports prediction, timing, and coordination of cognitive operations (Stoodley and Schmahmann 2009, D'Angelo and Casali 2012). Early theoretical models proposed that disruption of cerebello–thalamo–cortical circuits lead to “cognitive dysmetria”, reflecting impaired coordination of mental activity in SZ (Andreasen, Paradiso et al. 1998, Andreasen and Pierson 2008). Converging evidence from neuroimaging and clinical studies supports cerebellar involvement in cognitive deficits and symptom dimensions observed in SZ (Rolls, Cheng et al. 2020, Faris, Pischedda et al. 2024).

This framework is further supported by evidence that core symptoms of psychosis, including hallucinations, delusions, and thought disorder, can be interpreted as failures of predictive mechanisms, particularly in distinguishing self-generated from external signals, with emerging evidence implicating cerebellar dysfunction in these processes (Moberget and Ivry 2019).

Despite strong evidence for cerebellar involvement at the systems level, the cellular and microcircuit mechanisms underlying these alterations remain poorly defined. Understanding how specific neuronal

populations contribute to circuit dysfunction is essential to link microscale pathology to predictive dysfunction and psychosis.

Accordingly, this review focuses on the cerebellum as a critical node in SZ pathophysiology, with emphasis on its role in cognitive dysfunction. A comprehensive overview of neurobiological alterations in SZ has been provided previously (Faris, Pischetta et al. 2024); here, we specifically examine cerebellar pathology at the cellular and microcircuit level. We synthesise evidence from human and animal studies to characterise alterations in key cerebellar neuronal populations, including Purkinje cells, granule cells, and inhibitory interneurons. By integrating these findings, we aim to define how cell-type-specific alterations disrupt cerebellar computation and contribute to impaired predictive processing and large-scale network dysfunction associated with psychosis.

This assessment is based on a structured search of PubMed, Web of Science, and Scopus databases, focusing on studies investigating cerebellar alterations in SZ. We included human postmortem studies, neuroimaging studies, and experimental rodent models relevant to SZ pathophysiology. Priority was given to recent studies and those providing cellular, circuit, and mechanistic insights. Evidence was synthesised qualitatively, with emphasis on convergent findings across levels of analysis.

1.2 The cerebellum in cognition and brain network coordination

The cerebellum has traditionally been regarded as a structure for motor coordination and control (see **Text Box 1**). Through its extensive reciprocal connections with motor, premotor, and sensory cortices, the cerebellum fine-tunes voluntary movements, regulates timing, and supports motor learning. Lesions of the cerebellum produce characteristic motor deficits, including ataxia, dysmetria, impaired eye movements, and deficits in sensorimotor synchronisation, underscoring its essential role in predictive motor control (Ivry and Spencer 2004, Manto 2008, Glickstein, Strata et al. 2009). This classical motor-centric view has been substantially revised. Accumulating anatomical, physiological, and neuroimaging evidence demonstrates that the cerebellum is densely interconnected with associative and limbic cortices, positioning it as a key hub for coordinating motor, cognitive, and affective processes. These cerebrocerebellar loops support functions extending well beyond movement execution, including timing, prediction, working memory, language, and emotional regulation (Ito 2006, Stoodley and Schmahmann 2009, D'Angelo and Casali 2012, Schmahmann 2019).

Text Box 1

Cerebellar operations

The cerebellum receives motor commands from the primary motor cortex and compares predicted sensory feedback with actual sensory input. This network exhibits three main functional properties: adaptive filtering, input pre-processing, and error-driven supervised learning (Dean and Porrill 2008, Dean, Porrill et al. 2010, Wilson, Anderson et al. 2019). (I) Adaptive filtering allows the cerebellum to modify internal parameters through learning in the granular and molecular layer circuits (Dean and Porrill 2008, Dean, Porrill et al. 2010, Wilson, Anderson et al. 2019). (II) Input pre-processing is mainly performed by the granular layer, causing pattern separation (D'Angelo and Casali 2012, Cayco-Gajic and Silver 2019, Casali, Tognolina et al. 2020); (III) Error-driven learning requires an instructive signal that leads to appropriate adjustments in the adaptive filter through supervised learning. These three operations involve signals through the mossy fibre (mf), parallel fibre (pf), and climbing fibre (cf) systems and several specialised mechanisms in the neurons and synapses of the circuit (Hansel, Linden et al. 2001). Acquiring new motor or cognitive skills typically entails transitioning from a controlled to an automatic processing mode, where the behaviour initially requires problem-solving and attention and becomes progressively more efficient, stereotyped, and significantly less dependent on attention (Koziol and Lutz 2013).

1.2.1 The cerebellum as a predictive and integrative brain structure

A defining feature of the cerebellum is its highly conserved anatomical organization and uniform microcircuit architecture across lobules and functional domains. Despite the diversity of behaviours it supports, cerebellar computation relies on a canonical circuit composed of mossy fibers, granule cells, Purkinje cells, interneurons, and deep cerebellar nuclei (see **Text Box 2**). This structural regularity supports the idea that the cerebellum implements a common computational principle across motor and non-motor domains (Marr 1969, Ito 2006, D'Angelo 2018). Within this framework, the cerebellum is thought to generate internal forward models that predict the sensory consequences of actions and cognitive operations. By comparing predicted and actual outcomes, cerebellar circuits compute

prediction errors that are used to update ongoing behaviour and future responses. These predictive mechanisms are supported by extensive synaptic plasticity at multiple sites within the cerebellar cortex and deep nuclei, enabling rapid adaptation and learning (D'Angelo 2014, Raymond and Medina 2018). This predictive coding function is not restricted to motor control. The same computational architecture is engaged during cognitive and perceptual tasks, suggesting that cerebellar microcircuits contribute to the temporal coordination, sequencing, and optimisation of distributed brain activity. As such, the cerebellum operates as an integrative structure that refines information processing across large-scale brain networks rather than acting as a purely motor module (D'Angelo and Casali 2012, Castellazzi, Bruno et al. 2018).

Disruption of these predictive and integrative cerebellar computations has been implicated in SZ and psychosis, where core symptoms such as hallucinations, delusions, and thought disorder can be understood as reflecting dysfunctional predictive mechanisms, including impaired attenuation of self-generated sensory signals and altered use of contextual predictions (Andreasen, Paradiso et al. 1998, Andreasen and Pierson 2008, D'Mello, Crocetti et al. 2015, Moberget and Ivry 2019).

In psychosis, dysfunctional predictive mechanisms arise from an imbalance between prior beliefs and sensory

Text Box 2

Cerebellar anatomical organisation

The cerebellum is anatomically organised into two lateral hemispheres and a central vermis, which together constitute its macroscopic structure. Two major fissures, the primary and the posterolateral fissures, divide the cerebellum into three distinct lobes. The primary fissure separates the anterior lobe from the posterior lobe, while the posterolateral fissure delineates the boundary between the posterior lobe and the flocculonodular lobe. This tripartite division reflects both the phylogenetic and functional specialisation of the cerebellar cortex, supporting distinct sensorimotor, vestibular, and integrative functions (Cerminara, Lang et al. 2015, Jimshelishvili and Dididze 2025). The anterior lobe comprises lobules I–V, the posterior lobe includes lobules VI–IX, and lobule X belongs to the flocculonodular lobe. The cerebellar cortex consists of three layers, each containing a set of neurons and fibers: the outermost layer, the molecular layer (MLI), contains basket (BC) and stellate cells (SC), along with parallel fibers (pf) from GrCs, cf from the inferior olive nucleus (IO), and PC dendrites. Below the molecular layer, the Purkinje cell layer (PL) consists of a monolayer of PC somata. The innermost layer, the granule cell layer (GL), contains GrCs bodies, GoCs, Lugaro (LC), Unipolar Brush Cells (UBCs), and mossy fibers (mf) from precerebellar regions. Other neurons, such as candelabrum, and LCs, even though been known for decades, their connectivity and function were only recently thoroughly investigated (Hull and Regehr 2022). The white matter, located below the GCL, contains the deep cerebellar nuclei (DCN) (Ito 2006). Despite regional variations in cell size, density, and molecular composition, the cerebellar circuit maintains a highly organised and regular structure. It integrates precerebellar input through mf, making synapses onto excitatory GrCs and partially on inhibitory GoCs, while cfs comes from the IO form excitatory synapses on a subset of PC dendritic spines.

input, leading to aberrant precision weighting and maladaptive inference (Sterzer, Adams et al. 2018). Within this framework, disrupted prediction error signalling impairs context-dependent processing and cognitive control (Abboud, Noronha et al. 2017). At the sensory level, reduced attenuation of self-generated signals and impaired multisensory integration contribute to aberrant salience attribution and

perceptual disturbances, consistent with hierarchical disruption of predictive processing (Sterzer, Adams et al. 2018, Moberget and Ivry 2019).

1.2.2 The cerebellar contribution to cognition and the “dysmetria of thought”

Functional specialization within the cerebellum follows a topographic organization, with anterior lobules (I-III) primarily associated with sensorimotor functions and posterior lobules (IV-IX), including Crus I and Crus II, preferentially engaged during cognitive and affective tasks. Neuroimaging and lesion studies consistently demonstrate that damage to posterior cerebellar regions results in deficits in executive function, working memory, language, social cognition, and emotional regulation, while sparing basic motor control (Schmahmann and Sherman 1998, Stoodley and Schmahmann 2009). These observations led to the formulation of the “*dysmetria of thought*” hypothesis, which extends the cerebellar role in motor coordination to cognition and emotion. According to this model, cerebellar dysfunction disrupts the smooth coordination of mental operations, leading to deficits in prioritization, timing, prediction, and contextual modulation of thought and behaviour (Schmahmann 1998, Schmahmann 2019). Cerebellar contributions to cognition are mediated by closed-loop cerebello-thalamo-cortical circuits linking the cerebellum with prefrontal, parietal, and limbic cortices. Through these loops, cerebellar output modulates cortical processing, influencing cognitive flexibility, emotional responses, and the integration of multisensory information (D'Angelo and Casali 2012, Castellazzi, Palesi et al. 2014, Bostan and Strick 2018). This network architecture provides a mechanistic basis for understanding how cerebellar dysfunction may contribute to neuropsychiatric disorders characterized by impaired prediction, cognitive coordination, and affective regulation.

1.3 The cerebellum in SZ: network dysfunction and pathophysiological relevance

1.3.1 System-level dysfunction

SZ is highly associated with brain structural and functional abnormalities in the cerebral cortex and subcortical structures. Studies consistently report reduced volumes in frontal and temporal lobes, disrupted neural connectivity, and altered neurotransmitter dynamics within these regions (Wright, Rabe-Hesketh et al. 2000, Dean 2002, Cannon, van Erp et al. 2003, Karlsgodt, Sun et al. 2010, Zhao, Zhu et al. 2018, McCutcheon, Reis Marques et al. 2020, Khalil, Hollander et al. 2022, Sone, Koshiyama et al. 2022, Faris, Pischedda et al. 2024). In the late 90s, Andreasen introduced the "cognitive dysmetria" model, proposing that impaired interactions between the prefrontal cortex, thalamic nuclei, and cerebellum disrupt efficient information processing (Andreasen, Paradiso et al. 1998). Since then, increasing evidence has highlighted cerebellar abnormalities as a key contributor to SZ pathophysiology (Andreasen and Pierson 2008, Yeganeh-Doost, Gruber et al. 2011, Bernard and Mittal 2015, Cao and Cannon 2019, Faris, Pischedda et al. 2024) through their impact on cortical processing (Andreasen and Pierson 2008, Yeganeh-Doost, Gruber et al. 2011, D'Mello, Crocetti et al. 2015, Mapelli, Soda et al. 2022).

The cerebellum, now widely acknowledged for its involvement in cognitive, affective, and social functions (D'Angelo and Casali 2012, Schmahmann 2019, Jacobi, Faber et al. 2021), demonstrates structural and functional alterations that can result in cerebellar cognitive affective syndrome (CCAS) along with other neurological disorders, such as ataxia and dysarthria (Schmahmann and Sherman 1998). The cerebellar ubiquitous connections with brain regions involved in higher cognitive functions support its role in fine-tuning mental processes. Emerging evidence indicates that cerebellar abnormalities contribute substantially to SZ by modulating cortical processing (Palesi, Tournier et al. 2015, Palesi, De Rinaldis et al. 2017, Schmahmann 2019, Jacobi, Faber et al. 2021, Faris, Pischcedda et al. 2024). Notably, cerebellar stimulation, particularly targeting the vermis/midline, has shown potential in alleviating negative and depressive symptoms in SZ, enhancing frontal-cerebellar connectivity, and modulating the abnormal neuro-oscillations associated with the disorder (Escelsior, Belvederi Murri et al. 2019, Hua, Abram et al. 2022, Faris, Pischcedda et al. 2024). Thus, this region emerges as a compelling target for novel therapeutic strategies to rescue SZ-related cognitive impairments (Faris, Pischcedda et al. 2024).

Converging evidence from neuroimaging, postmortem analyses, electrophysiology, and transcriptomics indicates alterations in the cerebellum at macro and microscale levels, which in turn, play a central role in SZ pathophysiology (see (Faris, Pischcedda et al. 2024)). Recent evidence further shows that SZ-related brain signatures include cerebellar alterations within distributed prefrontal–limbic networks associated with cognitive dysfunction (Koutsouleris, Vetter et al. 2026).

At the macroscopic level, patients exhibit consistent grey matter volume and cortical thickness reductions in cerebellar hemispheres and the vermis, alongside disrupted cerebello-thalamo-cortical and cerebello-prefrontal functional and structural connectivity. Particularly, cerebellar lobules Crus I–II, VI, VIIIB, VIIIA, and IX are consistently implicated in executive function, working memory, and cognitive flexibility, with lesions producing deficits paralleling prefrontal syndromes (Schmahmann and Sherman 1998, Argyropoulos, van Dun et al. 2020). Structural MRI reveals grey matter reduction in these regions, especially Crus II, correlating with age, illness duration, and cognitive decline (Moberget, Alnæs et al. 2019, Li, Liu et al. 2022). Functional imaging shows altered cerebellar-cortical connectivity and reduced task activation (Zhuo, Wang et al. 2018, He, Luo et al. 2019, Moussa-Tooks, Rogers et al. 2022, Kang, Chung et al. 2024).

Moreover, alterations in the cerebellar circuitry are closely associated with dysregulation of key neurotransmitters and neuromodulators, particularly involving glutamate, gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), acetylcholine, serotonin, and dopamine (Faris, Pischcedda et al. 2024). These systems are essential for maintaining the balance of excitatory/inhibitory (E/I) signalling at both the local cerebellar microscale level and the macroscale level of activity and connectivity. Additionally, recent evidence has shown deficits in predictive recalibration of action-outcome timing in SZ. Functional neuroimaging indicates that healthy individuals reduce middle frontal gyrus activity after temporal recalibration, a

modulation absent in SZ. In addition, recalibration engages bilateral cerebellar activation during cross-modal transfer in controls, a response significantly diminished in SZ. These findings implicate disrupted frontal and cerebellar mechanisms in impaired prediction updating and multisensory integration in SZ (Schmitter and Straube 2026).

Indeed, cerebellar involvement in SZ is mechanistically supported by its role in predictive processing (Picard, Amado et al. 2008, Bernard and Mittal 2015). Cerebellar circuits implement internal models that anticipate sensory and cognitive outcomes, while prediction errors are computed through the comparison between expected and actual inputs (D'Angelo and Casali 2012, Popa, Hewitt et al. 2012, Popa and Ebner 2018). Impairment of this process leads to abnormal updating of internal representations, which has been implicated in core features of psychosis, including aberrant salience, disorganised thought, and perceptual disturbances (Andreasen and Pierson 2008, Shinn, Baker et al. 2015). Through its dense connectivity with prefrontal, thalamic, and limbic regions, cerebellar dysfunction can propagate across large-scale brain networks, contributing to impaired integration of internal and external information.

1.3.2 In search of cellular-level alterations in SZ

Advancing our understanding of cerebellar pathology at the microscopic level will clarify alterations in cellular and microcircuit architecture that may represent either primary pathological mechanisms or compensatory adaptations. Moreover, defining neuronal impairments is essential to unravel the nature of cerebellar involvement in SZ, shed light on its underlying pathophysiology, and inform the development of targeted treatments.

This review comprehensively examines neuronal changes in the cerebellum by synthesising evidence on morphological, structural, and physiological abnormalities in key cerebellar neuronal populations (i.e., PC, GrC, and inhibitory interneurons MLI) and by integrating findings from studies on humans and animal models of SZ. As discussed in our previous review, alterations in cerebellar circuitry are increasingly implicated in SZ. Growing evidence suggests that understanding these cellular disruptions is crucial for elucidating the disease's pathophysiology (Faris, Pischedda et al. 2024). Although SZ is characterised by cell-specific neuropathology and multiple neurodevelopmental mechanisms (Notaras, Lodhi et al. 2022), cerebellar cell-specific alterations remain incompletely explored. Disruptions in cerebellar function may arise from changes in the morphology and activity of key neuronal types, spanning structural, numerical, and functional modifications, and may collectively contribute to the cognitive and motor deficits observed in SZ. In the following sections, we will examine cerebellar neuronal population alterations observed in SZ, drawing upon evidence from both human postmortem studies and rodent models. These investigations provide insights into the cellular and molecular changes within the cerebellum associated with SZ, enhancing our understanding of its pathophysiology.

Despite robust evidence for cerebellar involvement at the systems level, the cellular and microcircuit mechanisms underlying these alterations remain poorly defined. While macroscopic changes suggest early and region-specific vulnerability, it remains unclear how disruptions at the level of cerebellar neurons translate into network-level dysfunction. Addressing this gap requires a shift from global imaging findings to cell-type-resolved analyses of cerebellar cortical architecture.

Accordingly, this review aims to provide a cell-type-resolved synthesis of cerebellar cortical alterations in SZ. We integrate evidence from human postmortem studies and animal models to characterise morphological, numerical, synaptic, and functional abnormalities in Purkinje cells, granule cells, inhibitory interneurons, and glial populations. By organizing findings across experimental systems, we seek to define convergent cellular signatures of cerebellar dysfunction and establish a coherent framework linking microscopic pathology to altered cerebellar circuitry in SZ.

2. Purkinje cell alterations in SZ

PCs are key components of the cerebellar circuitry and are one of the largest and most complex neurons of the central nervous system (Seto, Nakatani et al. 2014). Thus, it is not surprising that PCs have been extensively investigated across various pathological models. PCs are inhibitory neurons that play a crucial role in integrating excitatory and inhibitory inputs and generating the cerebellar output (Hirano 2018). As the sole output neurons of the cerebellar cortex, PCs regulate the timing, precision, and coordination of signals transmitted to thalamo-cortical networks (Andreasen and Pierson 2008, Abboud, Noronha et al. 2017). Alterations in PC structure and function are therefore expected to disrupt prediction error signaling and the updating of internal models, processes that are critical for cognitive function and are impaired in SZ (Cao and Cannon 2019).

It is worth noting that PCs have been extensively studied in animals, while their morphological and intrinsic properties in humans have been partially addressed only recently. High-resolution morphological reconstructions and limited electrophysiological data from human PCs *ex vivo* have provided new insights into their structural and functional differences compared to rodent PCs. While both species exhibit similar fractal dendritic structures, human PCs are significantly larger, with an estimated 7.5-fold increase in dendritic spine number due to comparable spine density ($2/\mu\text{m}$) and greater dendritic length. Unlike rodent PCs, which typically extend a single primary dendritic trunk, human PCs often generate 2–3 main trunks. Despite these morphological differences, intrinsic electroresponsiveness remains comparable between species. However, computational multi-compartmental models indicate that human PC dendrites can process approximately 6.5 times more input patterns than their rodent counterparts (Masoli, Sanchez-Ponce et al. 2024), suggesting that while the fundamental electrophysiological properties of PCs have been conserved through evolution, the increased dendritic complexity in human PCs enhances their computational capacity, potentially contributing to more

sophisticated cerebellar processing. PCs provide inhibitory signals to fine-tune and modulate the cerebellar output to other parts of the brain (Mapelli, Solinas et al. 2014, Nieuws, Mapelli et al. 2014).

Electrical stimulation of PCs and DCNs has been shown to induce a sustained increase in dopamine release in the prefrontal cortex, highlighting a functional link between cerebellar output and dopaminergic activity in areas associated with cognitive control. Thus, misconnections potentially exacerbate symptoms in SZ (Mittleman, Goldowitz et al. 2008). Furthermore, diminished cerebellar interactions with the basal ganglia-dopamine network have been implicated in the dysregulation of motivational processes, which is a critical domain affected in SZ (Yoshida, Oñate et al. 2022). Further, cerebellar dopamine depletion indirectly impacted spike-time-dependent plasticity at the pf-PC synapses, degrading associative motor learning (Gambosi, Sheiban et al. 2023).

Postmortem studies and diverse rodent models of SZ provide compelling evidence of PC alterations. Structural impairments include reductions in cell volume, linear density, and morphometric properties, while functional deficits affect electrophysiological properties, intracellular signaling, and neurotransmitter release. Recent findings highlight significant structural and functional changes in PCs, underscoring their critical role in SZ pathophysiology. Studies consistently report abnormal activity patterns that disrupt cerebellar signaling pathways involved in motor control, cognition, and emotional regulation. These deficits compromise the cerebellar modulatory functions, positioning PCs as key players in the neurobiological mechanisms of SZ. Clinical investigations and experimental models further confirm these alterations, revealing neuronal degeneration, synaptic dysfunction, and irregular firing activity as defining features of PC pathology in SZ.

The following sections will examine the evidence of morphological and functional abnormalities of PCs in SZ, based on findings from human postmortem studies and animal models.

2.1 Human postmortem studies

2.1.1 Morphological signature

Understanding the neuropathology of SZ is limited in humans due to multiple constraints. Most postmortem and neuroimaging studies have small sample size, which reduces statistical power and reproducibility, and brings along issues with clinical heterogeneity, medication effects, poor tissue quality, and sampling bias. Most studies are cross-sectional and lack data from early stages. This is particularly relevant when attempting to elucidate the mechanistic contributions of the cerebellum to disease pathogenesis. Despite that, several studies have highlighted significant structural impairment in PCs in SZ post-mortem tissues (see **Figures 1 & 2**).

Smaller PCs were reported in the cerebellar vermis of elderly SZ subjects compared to those with nonpsychiatric conditions, with no observable difference in PC linear density (Tran, Smutzer et al. 1998). A subsequent study reported a 20% reduction in PC linear density, along with a 20% decrease in the mean number of PCs (neurons per millimetre) in SZ (but also in bipolar disorder, BP, patients)

compared to non-psychiatric controls. This linear difference could be a common characteristic in SZ and BP, with a significant reduction in PC populations observed in both conditions (Maloku, Covelo et al. 2010). This reduction was mainly associated with reelin downregulation (50% reduction in expression), which was confirmed by a comparative mouse model study (see below (2.2.1)) (Maloku, Covelo et al. 2010). In addition to reelin deficits, changes in PCs expressing glutamic acid decarboxylase 67 (GAD67), a key enzyme in GABA synthesis, have been reported. SZ cerebellar tissues show marked reductions in GAD67 mRNA and protein levels (Guidotti, Auta et al. 2000). The downregulation of GAD67 in SZ may contribute to PC loss, similar to what was observed in reeler mice (Maloku, Covelo et al. 2010). A severe reduction in PC number was evidenced in a case of ataxia (SCA6) where the alpha1 subunit of the Cav2.1 calcium channel was affected (Tashiro, Suzuki et al. 1999). The patient, who showed slowly progressive mental disorders and gait ataxia, was clinically diagnosed at 39 years to have cortical cerebellar atrophy and SZ symptoms. At the autopsy, the main histopathological findings included a severe loss of PCs and IO cells. In this case, the number of PCs had decreased severely compared to that in either olivopontocerebellar atrophy or age-matched control cases, and PCs in the cerebellar hemisphere were more affected than those in the vermis. The neurons of the dentate nucleus and pontine nuclei were well-preserved, and no pathological changes were seen in the cerebral cortices or basal ganglia (Tashiro, Suzuki et al. 1999).

In contrast to the abovementioned findings, a stereological study reported no detectable numerical changes in PCs and GrCs in the cerebellum of post-mortem chronic SZ patients. This finding challenges the assumption that cerebellar structure is consistently altered in SZ, particularly in the chronic stages of the disorder (Andersen and Pakkenberg 2003). In a small cohort study of adult males with the onset of SZ, no significant differences were observed in the linear density of PCs in the cerebellar vermis, despite the presence of hippocampal abnormalities in the same individuals (Lingärde, Jönsson et al. 2000). It was argued that vermis abnormalities observed in some SZ patients may constitute a subsyndrome, possibly related to autistic disorders, in which cerebellar abnormalities are well corroborated (Lingärde, Jönsson et al. 2000). The absence of significant changes in cell volume or number suggests that the cerebellum may not undergo substantial morphological alterations in SZ at disease onset, despite other neuropathological features. However, this does not exclude the possibility of functional and/or structural changes or alterations in cerebellar connectivity, which could contribute to motor and cognitive deficits.

Despite this, the cellular architecture and overall structural compartments were found to be compromised in SZ. Indeed, one prominent finding using the Golgi method and 3D reconstructions of PCs evidenced substantial structural abnormalities in PCs of the upper surface of the right cerebellar hemisphere, including dendritic tree complexity due to a reduction in distal and terminal dendritic branches, along with a decrease in dendritic spine density, suggesting compromised neuronal connectivity and plasticity (Mavroudis, Petrides et al. 2017). Remarkably, the 3D reconstructions of

PCs from SZ reveal prominent decreases in total dendritic length and extensive loss of distal branches, along with reductions in the dendritic tree area and volume. Specific alterations in branching structures, such as the daughter ratio and bifurcation tilt, contribute to these overall reductions, further substantiated by Sholl analysis, showing restricted dendritic fields, especially beyond 150 μm from the soma (Mavroudis, Petrides et al. 2017). Although the thickness of the molecular layer was severely decreased in SZ brains, there was no statistical significance in the linear PC density, confirming the findings of previous evidence of Lingärde et al. (2000) and Tran et al. (1998).

At least three postmortem studies have reported no significant changes in the linear density of PCs in SZ. However, consistent alterations were observed at the level of somatic volume and microstructural organization. These morphological changes may reflect underlying molecular and genetic abnormalities previously documented in SZ. Notably, the loss of distal dendrites and dendritic spines results in a marked reduction in the synaptic surface area and the number of synaptic contacts formed by PCs, which contributes to the motor and cognitive dysfunctions frequently observed in SZ. Noting that, structural shift includes the presence of dystrophic and abnormal spines, features commonly linked to neurodevelopmental and neurological disorders (Akhgari, Michel et al. 2024).

An innovative human imaging finding indicates that cerebellar GABAergic signalling mediates hyperconnectivity in the cerebello-thalamo-cortical (CTC) circuit in SZ patients. These individuals exhibit significantly elevated GABA levels in the cerebellum, and cerebellar GABA has a significant mediating effect on CTC hyperconnectivity; notably, the unbalanced ratio of glutamate/GABA was partially normalized by cerebellar stimulation with TMS (Yao, Zhao et al. 2025). Given that, not only PCs but MLI and GoCs also are sources of GABAergic inhibition inside the cerebellar network, their combined activity delivered via the DCNs and thalamus, back to the neocortex (Diedrichsen, King et al. 2019), may underlie these connectivity changes. These structural alterations are expected to reduce synaptic integration capacity and impair the precision of cerebellar output, potentially disrupting timing-dependent coordination of cortical activity and contributing to cognitive deficits in SZ.

2.1.2 Synaptic receptor abnormalities

PCs from SZ patients exhibit alterations in neurotransmitter receptor distribution that may contribute to the disorder's pathophysiology. A receptor subtype implicated in SZ is the 5-HT_{1A} receptor (5-HT_{1A}AR), which exhibits abnormal persistence in the cerebellum, particularly in PCs. Normally, 5-HT_{1A}AR expression is high in the neonatal cerebellum but decreases during infancy (Slater, Doyle et al. 1998). Conversely, in SZ, 5-HT_{1A}AR remains elevated in adult cerebellar tissue, especially in vermal lobules I, II, IX, and X. This persistent expression is typically observed only during early neurodevelopment, suggesting a disruption in cerebellar neurotransmission. Since PCs are the primary output of the cerebellum, the altered receptor profile in these cells likely contributes to the cerebellar dysfunction observed in SZ. Additionally, in a SZ patient treated with clozapine, no restoration of normal 5-HT_{1A}AR

expression was observed, indicating that clozapine's effects may not be sufficient to affect the receptor's binding kinetics, thus limiting its therapeutic effect on receptor regulation (Slater, Doyle et al. 1998).

A reported colocalization shift in serotonin (5-HT) 5-HT_{2A} receptor (5-HT_{2A}AR) immunoreactivity from soma to dendrites. This abnormal distribution could stem from changes in serotonin innervation or increased agonist stimulation (Berry, Shah et al. 1996). Alterations in 5-HT_{2A}AR function involve not only changes in receptor-mediated membrane responses but also modifications in intracellular downstream signaling pathways (Eastwood, Burnet et al. 2001).

At a molecular level, there are substantial biochemical shifts in SZ associated with PC dysfunction, for instance, an increase in Semaphorin 3A (Sema3A) expression in the SZ cerebellum. Sema3A plays a critical role in axon guidance, and its elevation disrupts synaptic connectivity, which is supported by its inverse correlation with synaptic protein mRNAs (Eastwood, Law et al. 2003).

In addition to receptor alterations, abnormalities extended the molecular mechanism. For instance, altered nitergic mechanisms and calcium-dependent signal transduction have been observed in PCs from SZ. While PCs in controls show baseline nNOS expression, SZ patients exhibit a strongly increased number of nNOS-expressing PCs (Bernstein, Krell et al. 2001). Notably, during normal neurodevelopment, the expression of nNOS in human PCs typically declines. Hence, the elevated levels of nNOS in SZ suggest that PCs may remain in a more "immature" state, providing further evidence for neurodevelopmental disturbances in SZ. Remarkably, NO signaling influences cerebellar LTP and the adaptation of post-saccadic smooth pursuit movements. Excessive NO production could also affect cerebellar blood vessels, contributing to the increased blood flow observed in SZ. Moreover, elevated nNOS levels and NO have been shown to impair PC survival *in vitro* (Oldreive, Gaynor et al. 2012). A model of NO production and diffusion within a cerebellar spiking neural network framework demonstrated that NO diffusion modulates synaptic plasticity by dynamically adjusting learning rates based on activity patterns. This metaplastic mechanism enhances input selectivity and reduces interference, refining cerebellar learning (Trapani, Sartori et al. 2025).

Besides, NO signalling plays a role in the storage, uptake, and release of various neurotransmitters (Ohkuma and Katsura 2001), including glutamate, acetylcholine, noradrenaline, GABA, taurine, and glycine, and can diffuse across cell membranes to activate extra-synaptic receptors. It is additionally involved in peroxidation and reactive oxidative stress. Studies have demonstrated significant disturbances in NO levels in brain regions such as the cerebellum, hypothalamus, hippocampus, and striatum, as well as in the cerebrospinal fluid of SZ patients (Nasyrova, Ivashchenko et al. 2015).

In addition, a postmortem study examined HSP70, a cellular heat shock or stress protein, expression in the cerebellum of SZ patients. In this study, HSP70 immunoreactivity was significantly reduced in SZ patients compared to controls, particularly in the synaptic glomeruli of the granular cell layer and the cytoplasm and dendrites of PCs (Leonidas 2012). HSP70 is a stress protein involved in cellular

protection, and synaptic formation, memory formation, and its decreased expression in the cerebellum suggests a disruption of protective neural mechanisms (Leonidas 2012, Zatssepina, Evgen'ev et al. 2021). This reduction likely contributes to the cognitive dysfunctions observed in SZ, reinforcing the notion that even in the absence of detectable morphological changes, alterations in molecular and cellular function, such as impaired stress response, might play a significant role in the pathophysiology of the disorder.

Autoimmune dysfunction involving PC antibodies has been observed in SZ, suggesting a potential link between cerebellar autoimmunity and disease pathology. A study detected PC autoantibodies in 22.9% of SZ patients, while none were found in healthy controls, but were present in all patients with Paraneoplastic Cerebellar Degeneration (PCD), a well-established autoimmune disorder affecting PCs (Chiaie, Caronti et al. 2012). Particularly, SZ patients with these autoantibodies also exhibited markers of nonspecific immune activation, a pattern absent in PCD patients. A subsequent study detected the antibody level in the serum and cerebrospinal fluid from SZ patients against cerebellar PCs was serum 0%, CSF 2%. This suggests that PC-directed autoimmunity in SZ may not be a primary pathogenic mechanism but rather a consequence of broader immune dysregulation, particularly during the acute symptomatic phase (Endres, von Zedtwitz et al. 2022).

Dysfunctional PC activity in SZ has been implicated in associative learning deficits, particularly in eye-blink conditioning, a cerebellar-dependent process. A study investigated the effects of secretin, a neuromodulator that acts on PC and BCs, and found that its administration significantly improved eye-blink conditioning in SZ patients compared to a placebo. Given that PCs regulate cerebellar output by modulating DCN activity, these findings suggest that their dysfunction contributes to cognitive impairments in SZ (Bolbecker, Hetrick et al. 2009). The observed improvement after secretin administration supports the hypothesis that intracellular signaling abnormalities in PCs may underlie aspects of the disorder, highlighting the potential of cerebellar-targeted treatments in addressing cognitive deficits in the pathology.

PC disruption is further implicated in SZ by enhanced expression of D-amino acid oxidase (DAO) in surrounding Bergmann glia that might eventually disrupt glutamatergic neurotransmission. DAO degrades D-serine (Sasabe, Suzuki et al. 2014, Gonda, Ishii et al. 2022), a critical co-agonist of NMDARs; thus, reduced D-serine availability impairs NMDARs function, disrupting the E/I balance in PC, eventually altering cerebellar output. Immunohistochemical analysis of postmortem brain tissues from SZ patients has shown elevated DAO immunoreactivity in the cerebellum and medulla oblongata. In the cerebellum, these signals were strong in the molecular and PC layers, primarily in Bergmann cells but not in PCs. While the distribution pattern was similar to controls, the intensity was significantly increased, suggesting an aberrant glial response contributing to PC dysfunction (Ono, Shishido et al. 2009). Supporting this, a follow-up study revealed significantly lower serum levels of D-serine in SZ

patients compared to healthy individuals. D-serine, which binds to the NMDARs with a three-fold higher affinity than glycine, plays a crucial role in NMDAR function (Uzun Uysal, Tomruk et al. 2024). This reduction in D-serine leads to NMDARs hypofunction, a key factor in SZ pathophysiology. Antipsychotic treatment enhances these markers, suggesting their sensitivity to treatment and implicating NMDAR dysfunction in SZ (Uzun Uysal, Tomruk et al. 2024). This disruption of NMDARs activity eventually may contribute to cerebellar dysfunction, linking the altered D-serine metabolism and DAO expression to the underlying pathophysiology of the disorder.

These receptor and signaling abnormalities are likely to alter PC excitability and synaptic plasticity, leading to impaired modulation of cerebellar output and contributing to dysregulated E/I balance and aberrant information processing.

Overall, direct evidence from humans emphasises the critical role of PCs in SZ pathology (see **Figures 1&2**), encompassing reduced cell size, dendritic complexity, and number, indicating disrupted inhibitory signalling. Altered dendritic morphology and elevated nNOS expression suggest PCs may remain in a more immature state, pointing to neurodevelopmental disturbances. Increased DAO activity and decreased D-serine levels suggest impaired NMDAR function, further disrupting E/I balance. Immune and metabolic disturbances, including the production of autoantibodies against PCs and diminished HSP70 expression, combine these effects. Together, these alterations could eventually disrupt the cerebellar output, contributing to motor and cognitive deficits in SZ.

These human cellular alterations in PCs align with broader structural and functional disruptions observed in early-stage SZ. Specifically, cerebellar cortical abnormalities detected through neuroimaging further underscore the early and localized nature of these pathologies. It's worth noting that early involvement of cerebellar cortical abnormalities, as indicated by volumetric reductions in first-episode psychosis (Toyota, Mackinley et al. 2025), suggests that structural disruptions underscore the cerebellum's role in higher-order cognitive processes. Recent findings further support this perspective; volumetric reductions were observed in bilateral Crus I, Crus II, lobule VI and VIIa, left VIIb, and right lobules V and IX of the first episode of psychosis cerebella (van der Heijden, Hamoda et al. 2025). This progressive decline across study cohorts paralleled reductions in rostral middle frontal cortical thickness and centroparietal P300 (an event-related potential component observed in electroencephalography (EEG)). These findings highlight robust morphological disruptions in cerebellar sub-regions and their potential involvement in broader network dysfunction.

Together, evidence from human studies indicates that PCs in SZ exhibit consistent alterations in dendritic architecture, synaptic organisation, neurotransmitter signaling, and molecular pathways, even in the absence of uniform cell loss. These changes suggest impaired inhibitory output and disrupted synaptic integration. Given the central role of PC in shaping cerebellar output, such dysfunction is

expected to alter cerebello-thalamo-cortical communication and impair prediction error signaling, providing a potential cellular basis for cognitive and perceptual disturbances in SZ.

2.2 Animal model studies

Animal studies provide an essential experimental framework to investigate cellular and circuit mechanisms that cannot be directly examined in humans. Nevertheless, no animal model reproduces SZ as a diagnostic entity. Instead, experimental models reproduce specific biological perturbations associated with the disease risk, including genetic liability, neurodevelopmental insults, and neurotransmitter dysregulation. These approaches allow controlled investigation of how such perturbations affect cerebellar neuronal populations and microcircuit organisation.

These models are particularly relevant to SZ as they allow direct testing of how specific perturbations affect cerebellar computation and its contribution to cognitive and perceptual dysfunction.

In this section, we examine evidence from genetic, pharmacological, and neurodevelopmental models that reproduce SZ-relevant mechanisms and assess their impact on PC and the circuitry. Controlled physiological experiments can establish whether PC dysfunction is a primary driver of pathology or a late-stage consequence, clarifying its role in disease progression. While several limitations persist, various animal models have been proposed in the field of experimental neuroscience to explore the pathophysiology of SZ. These models include genetic, pharmacological, and neurodevelopmental animal models (Białoń and Wąsik 2022, Malik, Yaseen et al. 2023, Faris, Pischedda et al. 2024). Hence, in the next subsections (see **Figures 1 & 2**), we delve into the main findings in validating SZ-relevant animal models that evidence the potential of PCs' contribution to pathology.

2.2.1 Genetic animal models

Genetic rodent models carrying SZ-associated risk variants or exhibiting SZ-relevant genotypes and phenotypes provide mechanistic insight into cerebellar cellular and circuit abnormalities. These models recapitulate key features reported in human postmortem tissue, supporting their translational relevance, while enabling experimental interrogation of neurodevelopmental trajectories, synaptic physiology, and microcircuit dynamics that are inaccessible in humans. Alterations are most consistently observed in models with targeted disruption of SZ risk genes, in which PC development, synaptic integration, and firing properties are selectively affected (Faris, Pischedda et al. 2024). Together, these studies complement human evidence and delineate genetic pathways through which cerebellar PC pathology may emerge in SZ. It should be noted that, since the effect of genes is often pleiotropic, different pathologies may arise from the same gene mutation. For clarity, we attempt below a broad distinction between genetic evidence from SZ-linked models (humanised mouse mutations) and indirect evidence from other mutations altering neurodevelopment and neuronal or synaptic functions that can give insight into SZ.

2.2.1.1 Direct genetic evidence from SZ-linked models

Genetically defined models with established SZ risk genes demonstrate that disruption of SZ-linked genes is sufficient to induce PC structural and functional abnormalities. **EBP1** (ErbB3-binding protein 1), which is involved in brain development, regulation of gene expression, neuronal differentiation, and synaptic function regulation, interacts with the neuregulin-1 /ERB-B signalling pathway, which is one of the best supported biological pathways implicated in SZ. *Ebp1* conditional knock-out (cKO) mice exhibit severe cerebellar cytoarchitectural deficit, reduced cerebellar volume, and impaired PC development, emphasising the role of genetic vulnerability in SZ-related cerebellar alterations (Hwang, Kim et al. 2022). *Ebp1* cKO mice show a marked loss of PCs both on the sagittal and transverse plane. The number of PCs and the thickness of the molecular layer, where the dendritic branches are positioned, are reduced along with a reduction in the PC dendritic length. Furthermore, Golgi staining of PC dendrites shows a substantial decrease in spine density with irregular distribution, while GCs are not affected by *Ebp1* cKO (Hwang, Kim et al. 2022).

DISC1 (Disrupted-In-Schizophrenia-1) and DISC1 variants have been associated with neurodevelopmental disorders and several major psychiatric disorders, including SZ (Blackwood, Fordyce et al. 2001, Cash-Padgett and Jaaro-Peled 2013). Mutant mice with inducible and selective expression of a dominant-negative, C-terminus truncated human DISC1 (mutant DISC1), showed a significant shift in PC soma size at P21 (postnatal day 21), with an increase in the number of PC with small volume somas (750–1000 μm^3) and a decrease in large volume somas (4000–5000 μm^3) (Shevelkin, Terrillion et al. 2017). *DISC1* PCs show an increase in amplitude and frequency of miniature excitatory synaptic currents (mEPSCs) and in spontaneous firing. Alongside the morphological alterations (that were independent of inflammatory causes), a reduced expression of the Serine/arginine-rich splicing factor 2 splicing factor SC35 was observed. This may link *Disc1* mutations to deficits in RNA splicing and protein synthesis, potentially impacting PC maturation (Shevelkin, Terrillion et al. 2017). This heightened excitatory activity, possibly due to altered presynaptic release or postsynaptic sensitivity, underscores the mutant *Disc1* role in modulating cerebellar cellular physiology and morphology (Shevelkin, Terrillion et al. 2017). These structural and functional disruptions were correlated with behavioural abnormalities, particularly in male mice, who showed impaired social and recognition memory (Shevelkin, Terrillion et al. 2017).

The **22q11.2 Deletion Syndrome** (22q11DS), responsible for the DiGeorge syndrome, ranks among the greatest known genetic risk factors for the development of psychotic disorders in SZ patients. It confers a ~30% lifetime risk of SZ and ~50% risk of psychosis (Bassett and Chow 1999, Liu, Abecasis et al. 2002). It's also associated with movement disorders (Reyes, Grippe et al. 2025) and cerebellar atrophy (Racine, Garde et al. 2025). Notably, individuals with 22q11DS had 17.3% smaller total cerebellar volumes. In 22q11DS, the superior posterior lobule is disproportionately associated with cortical thickness in the frontal lobes and cingulate cortex. and (particularly Crus I) is associated with

psychotic symptoms (Schmitt, DeBevits et al. 2023). In an MRI study, a 28.6% volume reduction was observed in the paraflocculus and flocculus (PF/F), and an animal study showed a localised dysplasia in PF/F without overall brain or cerebellar volume loss (Eom, Schmitt et al. 2024).

The *Tbx1* (T-box transcription factor 1) gene, located on chromosome 22q11.2, is crucial for embryonic development and is deleted in the Df(16)1 mouse model, a genetically engineered mouse strain with a heterozygous deletion of a ~1 Mb region on chromosome 16, syntenic to the human 22q11.2 deletion. In acute PF/F slices, WT mice showed ~50% EPSP reduction following pf–cf co-stimulation (LTD), whereas Df(16)1/+ and Tbx1+/- mice showed LTP instead. These results indicate Tbx1 haploinsufficiency selectively impairs pf–PC LTD, consistent with context-specific VOR learning deficits, highlighting circuit-specific vulnerability in PF/F of 22q11DS models.

Also, the *DGCR2* (DiGeorge Syndrome Critical Region Gene 2) gene, located on 22q11.2, has been implicated in the pathophysiology of SZ. Mouse models with *Dgcr2* KO exhibit a significant sparseness in PCs, associated with gait abnormalities and trembling, and difficulty in balancing, indicating cerebellar cellular vulnerability, along with reduced latency to fall in the rotarod test (Mugikura, Katoh et al. 2016). This phenotype supports a link between *DGCR2* haploinsufficiency and disrupted cerebellar development, consistent with the structural and functional anomalies observed in both 22q11DS and SZ (Dickinson, Straub et al. 2014, Mugikura, Katoh et al. 2016, Ren, Luo et al. 2023). It should be noted that, although *DGCR2* stays on 22q11.2 and its loss consistently correlates with SZ, it also contributes to various neurological dysfunctions, including temporally limited deficits in locomotor activity, impaired motor coordination, and motor learning (Mugikura, Katoh et al. 2016) (see chapter below).

2.2.1.2 Mechanistic insights from neurodevelopment, channelopathy, and synaptopathy models

In addition to genetically defined SZ models, a broader class of neurodevelopmental and synaptic models provides mechanistic insight into cerebellar PC vulnerability. Although not specific to SZ, these models carry genetic variants implicated across neuropsychiatric disorders and reproduce cellular and circuit features that overlap with SZ pathology. As such, they offer indirect but informative evidence regarding mechanisms through which cerebellar dysfunction may emerge in SZ. These models do not recapitulate SZ as a diagnostic entity but instead illuminate conserved cellular mechanisms that may converge on cerebellar dysfunction across psychosis-related disorders.

Reeler mice, which express SZ-like cognitive impairments, mirror deficits in the human condition, including abnormalities in neuronal organisation and synaptic efficacy (Krueger, Howell et al. 2006). Reelin is an extracellular glycoprotein essential for neuronal migration and the correct positioning of neurons during brain development. Deficiencies or mutations in this gene cause severe defects in cortical lamination, lissencephaly, epilepsy, and are implicated in schizophrenia, autism, and bipolar disorder. The PC in Reelin (*Reln*) KO or heterozygous mice (reeler mice) shows reduced dendritic

arborization (shortened dendritic length and fewer branch points) along with poor orientation and 3D (rather than planar) organization. The reduced branch density, indicating compromised dendritic development, may impair the integration of synaptic inputs with other postsynaptic neurons, GCs and interneurons (Kim, Kwon et al. 2011). These extreme developmental defects affect not only the cerebellum but also the cortex and hippocampus, limiting their direct relevance to SZ. For SZ-relevant phenotypes, heterozygous Reeler mice ($Reelin^{+/-}$) are more appropriate, as they survive, display milder cerebellar PC deficits, and exhibit cognitive impairments reminiscent of SZ. Indeed, a comparative study of human data in the cerebella of heterozygous reeler mice, in which reelin expression is down-regulated by approximately 50% Maloku et al. (2010), found that the mutation was accompanied by 10-15% PC loss between 3 and 9 months of age, linking the reduction in the number of GABAergic PC to the reelin downregulation, as seen in the SZ and BP patients (see above (2.1.1)) (Maloku, Covelo et al. 2010). These findings highlight a potential molecular link between PC degeneration and altered inhibitory neurotransmission in psychiatric disease. The reduction in PC number and linear density implies that reelin, a crucial regulator of neuronal positioning during cerebellar development, plays a key role in maintaining the integrity of the cerebellar circuitry (Costa, Davis et al. 2001), reinforcing the concept that genetic alterations in cerebellar development are a relevant factor in SZ pathogenesis.

SCN2A gene (encoding for the alpha-subunit of the voltage-gated sodium channel Nav1.2) mutations, recognized as a significant risk factor for a broad spectrum of neurological disorders ranging from severe infantile epileptic encephalopathy to intellectual disability and autism spectrum disorder (ASD), have also been identified in SZ (Dickinson, Straub et al. 2014, Carroll, Woolf et al. 2016). Specifically, heterozygous loss of the *SCN2A*-encoded Nav1.2 sodium channels (as a model for ASD) in GCs leads to impaired high-frequency transmission to PCs and disrupts LTP essential for modulating VOR gain. VOR gain-down plasticity depends on LTP at pf-PC synapses. In *Scn2a^{+/-}*, GC dysfunction may impair this mechanism. In control mice, high-frequency burst stimulation of pf in acute cerebellar slices was used to induce robust LTP and reduced paired-pulse ratio (PPR) in PCs consistent with increased presynaptic release. This effect was observed in both the vermis and flocculus (Salin, Malenka et al. 1996). However, in *Scn2a^{+/-}* mice, an autistic model, LTP was absent using the same induction protocol. EPSC amplitude slightly decreased, and PPR remained unchanged. This reduction was blocked by the mGluR1 antagonist CPGCOEt, indicating co-activation of mGluR1-dependent LTD, which remained intact (Wang, Derderian et al. 2024). Notably, VOR plasticity can be restored in mice via a CRISPR-activator approach that enhances *Scn2a* expression, providing a measurable outcome for assessing therapeutic interventions (Wang, Derderian et al. 2024). The absence of VOR gain-down plasticity in mutant mice likely results from impaired synaptic potentiation at Pf-PC synapses. The post-induction decreases in PC firing observed *in vivo* may reflect intact LTD. Reduced intrinsic excitability in GCs was observed, consistent with Nav1.2 expression. Action potentials rose more slowly, and fewer spikes were generated under current injection, whereas the PC excitability was unaffected due to minimal Nav1.2 expression

(Wang, Derderian et al. 2024). These results indicate that impaired GC excitability underlies defective LTP and contributes to abnormal PC firing rate plasticity. Although initially evaluated as an autism model, the genetic mutation also confers risk for SZ, supporting its relevance to cerebellar pathophysiology in the SZ phenotype (Dickinson, Straub et al. 2014, Carroll, Woolf et al. 2016).

Missense variants of the *TRRAP* gene are associated with neuropathological symptoms, including psychosis-like symptoms in SZ (Mavros, Brownstein et al. 2018), although this model doesn't directly deal with SZ pathological (Achilly, He et al. 2021). *Trrap* deletion in PCs in murine models results in an age-dependent loss of neurons, leading to neurodegeneration (Tapias, Lázaro et al. 2021). Remarkably, PC in these models exhibit age-related axonal swellings, dendritic retraction, and reduced dendritic complexity without affecting the arborization, accompanied by alterations in the Sp1 signaling pathway (Achilly, He et al. 2021, Tapias, Lázaro et al. 2021).

The deletion of *Mecp2*, which causes autistic-like behaviour, may nonetheless provide indirect evidence highlighting the potential link between early-life genetic changes and long-term cerebellar dysfunction in psychotic disorders (Xu, Wang et al. 2023). PCs show reduced intrinsic excitability via SK channels, involving small-conductance calcium-activated potassium channels, PTP1B, and TrkB pathways that are critical for synaptic function and cerebellar plasticity (Xu, Wang et al. 2023). In these mice, reduced PC excitability was evident by postnatal day 90 (P90), marked by increased afterhyperpolarization and fewer action potentials. (Xu, Wang et al. 2023).

p75, a member of the tumor necrosis factor (TNF) receptor family, plays a critical role in neurodevelopment and neurogenesis (Catts, Al-Menhali et al. 2008). In p75-deficient mice, a significant reduction in neuroblasts, impaired neurogenesis, and behavioral abnormalities that suggest altered neurocircuitry were observed (Catts, Al-Menhali et al. 2008). This receptor has been implicated in SZ, particularly in regulating cellular survival and apoptosis (Chandra 2024). In the adult cerebellum, p75 is highly expressed in PCs, where it modulates their firing by regulating SK channel activity through the Rac1 signaling pathway. The absence of p75NTR leads to increased firing rates in PCs, primarily due to reduced activity of SK channels, which are crucial for regulating neuronal excitability (Tian, Tep et al. 2013, Tian, Tep et al. 2014). This dysregulation results in prolonged firing periods and diminished silence intervals, ultimately affecting cerebellar circuit processing (Tian, Tep et al. 2014). Furthermore, p75NTR is essential for the proper development of cerebellar granule neurons, and its absence can lead to excessive proliferation of these neurons, further disrupting cerebellar function (Zanin, Verpeut et al. 2019, Zanin, Pandya et al. 2023). Considerably, the PC firing deficits typically precede cell loss, suggesting that functional head structural alterations (Cook, Fields et al. 2021). However, while increased spontaneous firing in PCs is linked to disrupted cerebellar output, it is essential to consider that other factors, such as neuroinflammatory processes and genetic predispositions, may also contribute

to the pathophysiology of SZ, affecting PC firing patterns, complicating the interpretation of p75NTR role in this context.

Alterations in the glutamate receptor transmission mechanism are also related to SZ. Both Glutamate receptor delta-1 and delta-2 subunits (GluD1 and GluD2), encoded by **GRID1** and **GRID2** genes, can be found in the cerebellum but only GluD2 is expressed by PCs, whereas GluD1 is expressed by MLI. Recent studies suggest that SZ-linked variants, such as those associated with GluD2 disrupt PC function and synaptic plasticity (Allen, Garber et al. 2024). This disruption may significantly contribute to the cerebellar-related cognitive deficits observed in SZ. *GRID2* encodes a risk gene of SZ, and has deletions associated with SZ symptoms (Kushima, Aleksic et al. 2018). GluR δ 2 mutant demonstrates ataxia, impaired locomotion, and abnormalities in PCs, implicating GluD2Rs in cerebellar synaptic LTP (Kashiwabuchi, Ikeda et al. 1995, Kakegawa, Miyoshi et al. 2011) and synaptic organization (Mandolesi, Autuori et al. 2009). GluD2, Cerebellin1 (Cbln1), Neurexin and play crucial roles in maintaining proper cerebellar GCs and PC spines stability. This complex, which connects presynaptic terminals (to PC spines, regulates various mechanism (Dai, Patzke et al. 2021). Heterozygous **lurcher** mouse model carries a mutation in GluR δ 2 variant that makes the ionotropic receptor constitutively open, allowing large inward currents and depolarization at rest (Zuo, De Jager et al. 1997). This dysregulation can lead to PC apoptosis due to excitotoxicity. A spontaneous deletion in *GRID2* disrupts GluR δ 2 expression, leading to anterior cerebellar atrophy, reduced GC, and altered PC dendrite morphology and spine structure. These mice exhibit defective pf-PC synapse formation and abnormal cf innervation (Miyoshi, Yoshioka et al. 2014). Since in SZ, *GRID2* is identified as a risk gene, suggesting that similar GluR δ 2-mediated disruptions of GC-PC circuit function may underlie cerebellar structural and synaptic abnormalities observed in patients, which showed a large deletion in the coding region of the *GRID2* gene (Miyoshi, Yoshioka et al. 2014). These models highlight that diverse neurodevelopmental and synaptic perturbations converge on impaired PC integration and plasticity, suggesting a shared pathway through which cerebellar dysfunction may contribute to altered prediction and learning processes in SZ. Together, genetic models demonstrate that disruption of SZ-associated pathways directly affects PC development, synaptic integration, and firing properties. These alterations are expected to impair cerebellar output and disrupt its coordination with cortical networks, providing a mechanistic link between genetic risk and deficits in cognitive processing and behavioural regulation.

2.2.2 Pharmacological perturbation models relevant to SZ

Pharmacological models do not reproduce SZ as a diagnostic entity but act as perturbation paradigms that reproduce key neurochemical mechanisms implicated in SZ risk. In particular, manipulation of glutamatergic and dopaminergic signaling, such as NMDA receptor antagonism or dopamine elevation, allows controlled investigation of how dopaminergic and glutamatergic dysfunction impacts cerebellar circuitry, particularly PC connectivity and plasticity, thereby informing cellular processes that may be

vulnerable in SZ. The pharmacological rodent models are an additional experimental tool to study pathophysiology and behavioural phenotypes in diverse psychotic conditions (Malik, Yaseen et al. 2023) (for cerebellum see (Faris, Pischedda et al. 2024)). Various drug-induced approaches have emerged, each targeting distinct neurotransmitter systems that are essential for evaluating potential antipsychotic treatments. Among these, dopamine models, in which drugs like amphetamines are used to induce psychotic-like symptoms in rodents, and glutamate models, in which NMDAR antagonists, such as ketamine and phencyclidine (PCP), are introduced to mimic negative and cognitive symptoms associated with SZ (Malik, Yaseen et al. 2023).

Like genetic models, the **PCP** model exhibits PC-specific synaptic deficits in cerebellar regions, where afferent synaptic impairments lead to significant alterations in connectivity (Veleanu, Urrieta-Chávez et al. 2022). Long-term changes in PC synaptic connectivity were observed without alterations in the overall cerebellar cytoarchitecture or PC firing pattern (Veleanu, Urrieta-Chávez et al. 2022). Particularly, cf synapses exhibited region-specific changes, with an increased density of VGLUT2-positive boutons in lobule VI (cognitive lobules), while the synaptic territory was expanded in lobule VIII. Additionally, the volume of VGLUT2-labeled cfs boutons decreased, indicating a lobule-specific effect on cf-PC connectivity. In contrast, the electrophysiological properties of the cf-PC synaptic transmission showed no changes in PPR or overall charge transfer (total synaptic current at cf-PC synapses), except for an increased charge transfer in a subset of PCs. These results suggest that NMDARs antagonism during critical developmental periods selectively affect PC connectivity and synaptic organization, particularly within the olivocerebellar circuit, which may contribute to long-term functional deficits relevant to SZ (Veleanu, Urrieta-Chávez et al. 2022).

Ketamine-treated mice also demonstrated PC alteration involving apoptosis, pyknotic nuclei, irregular dark cytoplasm, and wide interstitial spaces around the cells. Along with overall histoarchitectural abnormal delineated of, molecular, Purkinje, and granular layers were, importantly, such modifications were reversed by *Carpolobia lutea* G. Don ethanol extract (natural product remedies) along with clozapine treatment (Omeiza, Bakre et al. 2023).

Other drug-induced animal models revealed alterations in PCs. For instance, repeated **methamphetamine** injections, which increase dopamine levels, caused significant changes in the organization of Aldoc (Zebrin II) stripes of PCs. Methamphetamine led to a high degree of fragmentation and lateral dislocation of stripes across various regions of the cerebellar vermis. Specifically, in the posterior region, these injections produced extensive fragmentation (up to forty dislocated stripes per cerebellum slice) and lateral dislocation. Conversely, central and nodular regions showed significant reductions in stripe area sizes, with noticeable lateral dislocation (Hamamura, Watanabe et al. 2004). Conversely, SLC1A6 (EAAT4) stripes, which encode a glutamate transporter associated with PCs, did not exhibit comparable dislocations or fragmentation, although mild

fragmentation was noted in the anterior region. These findings indicate that dopamine elevation selectively affects Zebrin II compartmentalization in PCs, while SLC1A6 mRNA distribution appears resistant to dopamine effects, suggesting different compartmental sensitivities to specific neurotransmitter systems (Hamamura, Watanabe et al. 2004). Additionally, repeated methamphetamine administration alters cerebellar compartmental excitability and metabolic markers in rats. Acute exposure induces c-fos mRNA in GrC and PC, particularly in Zebrin-like parasagittal bands (Hamamura, Ozawa et al. 1999). Chronic exposure reduces c-fos mRNA expression selectively in anterior and posterior cerebellar regions (lobules VII), while aldolase C mRNA decreases in distinct lobules (VI, IX), indicating region-specific changes in PCs' excitability and metabolic state. These alterations may contribute to motor sensitization, implicating the cerebellar hemisphere alongside striatal circuits in methamphetamine-induced behavioral changes (Hamamura, Ozawa et al. 1999)

These findings indicate that neurotransmitter imbalance directly alters PC connectivity and plasticity, supporting a model in which dopaminergic and glutamatergic dysregulation disrupt cerebellar contributions to prediction error signaling and adaptive behaviour.

2.2.3 Neurodevelopmental risk models implicating cerebellar Purkinje cell vulnerability

Neurodevelopmental risk models based on prenatal stress, maternal immune activation, or early toxic exposure do not model SZ as a diagnostic entity but capture well-established environmental risk factors for the disorder. These approaches provide etiologically relevant insight into how early-life insults intersect with critical periods of cerebellar development, revealing mechanisms through which PC structure and function may become persistently altered in SZ. Considering several animal models, maternal exposure to stress or infection during the gestational period strongly affects foetal neurodevelopmental processes and increases the risk of brain disorders, including SZ (Fineberg, Ellman et al. 2016). Given that SZ is increasingly recognized as a neurodevelopmental disorder, with early disruptions in brain maturation contributing to its pathophysiology (Stachowiak, Kucinski et al. 2013), Stress-induced animal models offer a reliable experimental framework to investigate SZ mechanisms. PCs undergo a complex genetic program that finalises synaptic integration by early childhood. However, this extended postnatal development makes the cerebellum highly vulnerable to environmental insults such as inflammation, hypoxia, and toxins (Sathyanesan, Zhou et al. 2019). Findings have shown that during a critical postnatal period, PCs are especially sensitive to inflammatory damage, which could disrupt their function and contribute to the cerebellar abnormalities observed in SZ (Wright, Hoffman et al. 2019). Recent single-cell genomic studies have shown that inflammation during critical periods of cerebellar maturation leads to overlapping transcriptional changes in PC and Goc3, key inhibitory neurons in the cerebellum (Ament, Cortes-Gutierrez et al. 2023) encompasses premature down-regulation of developmental gene expression programs, which could disrupt normal PCs function, and reveals the highly dynamic developmental trajectory of the cerebellum and potential for latent sensitive periods in early childhood (Ament, Cortes-Gutierrez et al. 2023).

Maternal stress alters cerebellar PC morphology, providing mechanistic insight into circuit-level disruptions observed in SZ (Pascual, Ebner et al. 2010, Pascual, Valencia et al. 2015). Prenatal restraint stress induced bimodal changes in vermal PC dendritic architecture: animals displayed dendritic overgrowth at P22 and P52, followed by a marked reduction in dendritic field at P82, with about 70% shrinkage compared to controls. This pattern suggests abnormal developmental overcompensation preceding dendritic atrophy in adulthood. A subsequent study demonstrated that environmental enrichment from P22 to P52 reversed the dendritic atrophy and reduced anxiety-like behaviour in prenatally stressed animals (Pascual, Valencia et al. 2015).

Proteomic profiling of postmortem cerebellar cortex from chronic SZ patients identified dysregulation of molecular pathways involved in cytoskeletal organization and mitochondrial bioenergetics (Vera-Montecinos, Rodríguez-Mias et al. 2021). Specifically, stress-responsive upregulation of cytoskeletal proteins and downregulation of mitochondrial components suggested disrupted axonal integrity and impaired energy metabolism, processes essential for PC function. These findings were validated in murine models subjected to early postnatal stressors, using a double-hit (**2HIT**) strategy, a model of SZ induced by exposing the offspring to maternal deprivation and social isolation, which indicated some molecular network alterations observed in SZ that were a consequence of different combinations of stress exposure during the late postnatal developmental phase of the cerebellum (Vera-Montecinos, Rodríguez-Mias et al. 2021), which replicated alterations in proteins enriched in PC-containing regions. Although no direct PC morphological data were reported, the proteomic signatures implicate PC vulnerability to stress-induced cytoskeletal remodelling and bioenergetic failure.

In another 2HIT model study involving maternal infection, PC loss was prominent, with a 38.4% reduction in Calbindin (+) PCs in lobules VIa-VIb, extending to lobules (II-IV, IX-X). At 9 weeks, PC loss was significantly greater than at 5 weeks, highlighting accelerated degeneration (Hikosaka, Parvez et al. 2025). Simultaneously, PCs axonal density decreased, and microglial density (Iba1⁺) increased in 2HIT animals, underscoring microglial reactivity in PC degeneration and axonal loss, supporting the hypothesis that inflammation mediates cerebellar dysfunction (Yamamoto, Kim et al. 2019). PC firing frequency was reduced in male MIA and 2HIT, reflecting reduced intrinsic excitability (Hikosaka, Parvez et al. 2025). Waveform analyses of an action potential showed an increase in input resistance, half-width, 10–90% rise time of action potential in Purkinje cells, suggesting the modulation of voltage-gated K⁺ and Na⁺ channels, which corroborated the reduced intrinsic excitability. Additionally, the stressed animals showed a significant reduction in PC axonal density, diameter, and g-ratio (equals the inner diameter of the axon divided by the total outer diameter including the myelin sheath) in the cerebellar dentate nucleus. Importantly, microglial depletion during 2HIT conditioning restored firing frequency to control levels, linking microglial activity to PC dysfunction and associated with altered cerebellar functional connectivity. These results suggest that 2HIT-induced inflammation disrupts PC

function and contributes to neurodegeneration, with microglia playing a key role in this process (Hikosaka, Parvez et al. 2025).

An earlier study using a maternal infection-induced mouse model (influenza/viral infection) revealed significant developmental deficits localized primarily to cerebellar lobule VII (Shi, Smith et al. 2009). In which adult offspring exhibited a 33% reduction in PCs linear density; notably, this change was not observed in any other cerebellar lobules, suggesting a selective impact on lobule VII rather than a generalized loss of PCs across the cerebellum. Furthermore, young offspring (P11) revealed similar reductions in PC counts, indicating that these alterations occur during early cerebellar development rather than being due to adult neurodegeneration. The presence of heterotopic PCs, misplaced calbindin-positive cells in lobules VI and VII in both young and adult offspring, suggests disrupted migration processes. The higher frequency of heterotopic PCs in P11 offspring compared to adults emphasizes that these anomalies manifest early, highlighting a critical window in cerebellar development susceptible to prenatal insults like maternal influenza infection. Notably, the molecular layer thickness was not affected, suggesting that the surviving PCs formed more synapses per cell to compensate. Overall, these findings underscore that cerebellar alterations occur during embryonic development and that the long-term impacts of prenatal factors on cerebellar structure and function, particularly concerning conditions like autism associated with PC deficits (Shi, Smith et al. 2009).

One widely used neurodevelopmental SZ model is the rodent treated prenatally with methylazoxymethanol acetate (MAM) at gestational day 17 (Lodge and Grace 2012, Lodge 2013). This model induces marked cerebellar alterations, including a 60% reduction in vermis surface area, GrCs depletion, and PC misalignment and dislocation (Hartkop and Jones 1977). PCs exhibit shortened dendrites with fewer branches and spines, many lacking presynaptic terminals, indicating disrupted synaptic connectivity (Hartkop and Jones 1977). Abnormal PC innervation patterns occur, such as multiple cf inputs, aberrant dendritic orientation, including growth into white matter, and enlarged cf terminal arbors (Bravin, Rossi et al. 1995). Notably, early cerebellar insults in this model produce hypoactivity, ataxia, tremors, and cognitive deficits, whereas later insults mainly cause hyperactivity (Ferguson 1996, Ferguson, Paule et al. 1996).

MAM treatment also results in a significant cerebellar weight reduction (up to 62%) due to PC loss, accompanied by cerebellar cortex atrophy and irregular PC distribution (Chen and Hillman 1986, Luthman, Eriksson-Nilsson et al. 1990). Neurochemical changes include increased tyrosine hydroxylase-immunoreactive fibers (+65%) and elevated serotonin and noradrenaline concentrations (+30-50%) in the cerebellum (Luthman, Eriksson-Nilsson et al. 1990). Group I metabotropic glutamate receptor binding sites increase in PCs, potentially compensating for decreased excitatory input, while Group II receptor expression shows delayed reduction (Becker, Gombos et al. 1996). Impaired synaptic pruning leads to persistent multiple cf innervation, further disrupting normal PC

signaling (Bravin, Rossi et al. 1995). Overall, the MAM model links early developmental cerebellar disruptions, particularly in PC morphology and connectivity.

However, not all studies report consistent alterations, suggesting case variability. For example, in a small cohort of adult-onset SZ men with documented hippocampal abnormalities, PC density in the cerebellar vermis was not altered compared to controls. This suggests that vermal abnormalities seen in some SZ patients may reflect a subsyndrome (Lingärde, Jönsson et al. 2000). Similarly, no differences were found in the ratio of displaced to normally placed PCs or PC density, challenging the hypothesis that PC migration abnormalities underlie these changes (Helmkamp, Bigelow et al. 1999). Additionally, it was reported that Nissl staining did not reveal apparent cell deformities of PCs in the flocculonodular and vermal regions, nor in the dentate nucleus. This observation implies that while the overall structure of the cerebellum may appear intact, subtle changes at the cellular level could still be present and relevant to the pathophysiology of SZ (Bernstein, Krell et al. 2001). This lack of significant difference in PC density contrasts with other findings of notable morphological alterations in dendritic structure and spine density, suggesting that PCs in SZ may exhibit functional disruptions despite an overall preserved cell count (Bernstein, Krell et al. 2001).

Collectively, neurodevelopmental models indicate that early-life insults disrupt PC maturation, connectivity, and excitability during critical developmental windows. These alterations are likely to produce long-lasting changes in cerebellar circuit function, impairing the formation and updating of internal models and contributing to cognitive and behavioural deficits characteristic of SZ.

Figure 1. Purkinje cell (PC) structural, numerical, and morphological alterations in schizophrenia (SZ): summary of evidence from Human postmortem and animal relevant models.

Figure 2. PC functional alterations in SZ: summary of evidence from Human postmortem and animal relevant model studies.

Together, these alterations (see section 2.) impair PCs integration, plasticity, and output, thereby disrupting cerebellar predictive computations and the coordination of large-scale brain networks. This might provide a mechanistic link between cellular pathology and cognitive dysfunction in SZ.

3. Granule cell alterations in SZ

Cerebellar GrCs, despite their small size (5-8 μm in diameter), represent more than half of all neurons in the central nervous system and play a pivotal role in cerebellar circuitry and function. GrCs are generated prenatally from the rhombic lip and then, after several rounds of mitosis, migrate from the external to the internal granular layer, where they mature and form synaptic connections (Burgoyne and Cambray-Deakin 1988). Due to their abundance, postnatal migration and maturation, the ease of isolation in cell cultures, and as an optimal model for examining cellular responses to stimuli, especially for electrophysiological assessments. These characteristics, coupled with their inducible apoptotic pathways in vitro, make cerebellar GrCs a valuable system for studying neurotransmitter effects,

neurotrophic signaling, and apoptotic mechanisms (Xifró and Rodríguez-Álvarez 2015). GrCs are the major cellular component of the GL, which also embeds GABAergic interneurons like GoCs and LCs. UBCs are the only other excitatory interneurons of the granular layers and are predominantly located in lobules IX, X, and sparsely in hemispheric portions of lobules IV-VI (Diño, Willard et al. 1999). Mf form synapses with GrCs, GoCs and DCNs, creating hundreds of synaptic rosettes inside a structure called a glomerulus. These rosettes contain mf, axon of GoCs, dendrites of GCs and in some cases a GoC basal dendrite too. The GrCs emit an axon ascending from GL to ML where it splits into two directions, forming pfs and making synapses on PCs, GoCs, SCs, and BCs.

3.1 Human postmortem studies

Similar to PCs, alterations in GrCs have been reported in several clinical and preclinical SZ studies (Eastwood, Cotter et al. 2001, Bullock, Cardon et al. 2008, Maloku, Covelo et al. 2010) (**Figure 3**). This includes a notable reduction in synaptic mRNA, such as synaptophysin (30%) specifically in the GL but not in the PC, and Complexin II (36%) relative to unchanged complexin I (Eastwood, Cotter et al. 2001). Additionally, alterations in the inhibitory neurotransmitter system observed in the cerebellum of SZ patients (see review (Faris, Pischetta et al. 2024)), in particular in GABAergic transmission at $\alpha 6$ GABA_ARs, which is expressed exclusively in GrCs (reviewed elsewhere (Chiou and Sieghart 2025)).

SZ is associated with selective deficits in GABAergic neurotransmission within the cerebellar lateral hemisphere, particularly involving GoCs. The study found decreased expression of GABA-synthesizing enzymes GAD65 and GAD67 and reduced levels of the GABA transporter VGAT-1, indicating impaired GABA synthesis and release. This dysfunction leads to diminished tonic inhibition of GrCs by GoCs, causing GrCs disinhibition, thus altering cerebellar output through PCs. Additionally, the GoCs selective NMDARs subunit NR2B was reduced, further implicating GoCs dysfunction and NMDARs hypofunction in SZ. Parvalbumin levels, expressed in PCs and SC/BC, remained unchanged, suggesting interneuron subtype-specific effects. Compensatory increases in extra-synaptic GABA AR subunits $\alpha 6$ and δ on GrCs, and elevated kainate receptor subunits GluR6 and KA2, were observed, reflecting increased GrC activity, thus GrC hyperexcitability. Reduced expression of modulators such as mGluR2 and nNOS synthase further suggests disrupted regulation of GABA release (Bullock, Cardon et al. 2008). These alterations in GrCs and GoCs contribute to aberrant cerebellar glutamatergic signaling in SZ, impacting the cortico-cerebellar-thalamic-cortical circuit and clinical symptoms. Effects of antipsychotic medications on these markers appear limited or variable, underscoring the need for treatments targeting GABA-glutamate imbalance in the cerebellum.

Given that GrCs are only regulated by GoCs inhibitory feedback, the GABA transmission modulation might lead to GrCs hyperexcitability, disrupting the E/I balance critical for cerebellar function. While GABAAR $\alpha 6$ and δ subunits were upregulated, this upregulation could reflect a compensatory mechanism within GrCs to counterbalance the diminished GABAergic input (Bullock, Cardon et al.

2008, Bullock, Bolognani et al. 2009). Subsequently, findings have shown increased levels of activity-dependent mRNAs such as GAP-43 and BDNF in SZ, whose expression is dependent on the activity of glutamatergic neurons, further suggesting GC hyperactivity, potentially contributing to the sensory-motor integration deficits observed in these patients. Notably, while the levels of GABA A δ , were positively correlated with those of GAP-43 and BDNF, the expression of the GABA α 6 subunit mRNA, which is activity-independent, remained unchanged (Paz, Andreasen et al. 2006). This differential expression pattern underscores dysfunctional glutamatergic signaling pathways in particular subtypes of GrCs population, those expressing GABA A δ , suggesting GrCs hyperactivity in SZ patients (Paz, Andreasen et al. 2006), implicating them in the pathophysiology of SZ and highlighting their role in the disorder's symptoms. Recent imaging data evidence high GABA levels associated with altered glutamate and GABA ratio that resulting in CTC hyper-connectivity, and was associated with the severity of clinical symptoms in patients, and cerebellar TMS partially normalised this ratio (Yao, Zhao et al. 2025).

Postmortem studies in SZ reveal multiple alterations in glutamate signalling and NMDAR subunits across cerebellar neurons. The NR2D subunit is overexpressed in the ML and GL of the right cerebellar hemisphere and vermis, suggesting compensatory hyperexcitability linked to glutamatergic hypoactivity in the right cerebellum, with no changes in NMDARs affinity (Schmitt, Koschel et al. 2010). While NR2C expression is decreased (Schmitt, Koschel et al. 2010) in the ML of the right cerebellum in patients carrying NRG1 risk alleles, indicating NMDARs hypofunction, as NR2C-containing receptors, as a major NMDARs subunit of GrCs, have prolonged glutamate-induced currents and reduced magnesium blockade (Monyer, Burnashev et al. 1994). Genetic factors affect brain function, with several SZ risk genes impacting NMDARs activity. These include dysbindin, metabotropic glutamate receptor 3, proline dehydrogenase, G72, DAAO, and NRG1, all linked to NMDARs hypofunction. Multiple studies have identified NRG1 as a key candidate gene for SZ (Harrison and Weinberger 2005, Law, Lipska et al. 2006). As mentioned earlier, the glutamatergic synaptic protein complexin II shows reduced mRNA and protein levels in GrCs (Eastwood, Cotter et al. 2001), supporting hypoglutamatergic deficits. Alterations in NMDA subunits affect GoCs, with decreased NR2B expression alongside reduced GABAergic markers (GAD65, GAD67, GAT-1), indicating impaired inhibitory control (Bullock, Cardon et al. 2008). Notably, antipsychotic treatment influences NMDA subunit expression: clozapine increases NR2C expression more than haloperidol, potentially restoring receptor function (Schmitt, Koschel et al. 2010). These findings collectively suggest disrupted NMDARs composition and glutamate transmission in cerebellar circuits in SZ (for altered glutamatergic signaling see review (Faris, Pischedda et al. 2024)), contributing to cognitive and motor symptoms through imbalanced excitatory-inhibitory regulation and lateralized cerebellar dysfunction. HSP70 expression is significantly reduced in SZ patients, particularly in the glomeruli (Leonidas 2012), further confirming altered GrCs function in SZ.

Despite these findings, direct evidence of GrC alterations in human SZ tissue remains limited. No postmortem studies have specifically quantified structural GrC abnormalities. Evidence from experimental models reproducing SZ-relevant genetic, developmental, or neurotransmitter perturbations indicates alterations in GrC development, excitability, and synaptic signaling (see following sections). Further investigation in human tissue is required to determine the extent and functional significance of these alterations in SZ pathophysiology.

3.2 Animal model studies

Animal models have provided important, albeit limited, insight into granule cell involvement in schizophrenia. Compared with PCs, granule cells have been less extensively investigated; however, convergent evidence from genetic and developmental models indicates that granule cell proliferation, intrinsic excitability, and synaptic integration are vulnerable to SZ-relevant perturbations. These alterations primarily affect mossy fiber–granule cell processing and parallel fiber output, with downstream consequences for cerebellar network function.

3.2.1 Genetic animal models

Genetic models carrying SZ-associated risk variants have provided mechanistic insight into GCs vulnerability within cerebellar circuits. One of the most direct lines of evidence involves the transcription factor **SP4**, which is reduced in the cerebellum of individuals with SZ and correlates with negative symptom severity (Pinacho, Villalmanzo et al. 2011, Pinacho, Villalmanzo et al. 2013). SP4 stability in GCs depends on NMDA receptor–mediated depolarization. Under conditions of NMDA receptor hypofunction, SP4 undergoes phosphorylation at serine 770, promoting its degradation and leading to impaired dendritic maturation and synaptic organization in GCs (Saia, Lalonde et al. 2014, Pinacho, Saia et al. 2015). These findings provide a molecular link between glutamatergic dysfunction and granule cell developmental abnormalities relevant to SZ.

The dysbindin-1–deficient (**Dtnbp1**^{–/–}) mouse represents a validated SZ risk model associated with cognitive and synaptic deficits (Van Den Bogaert, Schumacher et al. 2003, Papaleo and Weinberger 2011). Although cerebellum-specific phenotypes remain incompletely characterized, dysbindin-1 is enriched in mossy fiber terminals of the granule layer, forming parasagittal bands associated with UPB–rich regions (Benson, Newey et al. 2001, Sillitoe, Benson et al. 2003). This spatial organization suggests a role in regulating CG excitability and input integration. Indirect evidence from dystrophin-deficient mice indicates that disruption of dystrophin-dependent scaffolding alters dysbindin localization within cerebellar glomeruli, supporting a role for dysbindin in stabilizing GC synaptic architecture.

Altered GC development has also been reported in mice overexpressing **VGF**, a neuropeptide upregulated in SZ and associated with symptom severity (Mizoguchi, Minakuchi et al. 2018, Mizoguchi, Shimazawa et al. 2019). VGF overexpression leads to reduced cerebellar volume, hypoplasia of the granule layer, and impaired proliferation of GC precursors during early postnatal development, without

overt PC loss. These alterations are accompanied by SZ-like behavioral phenotypes that are responsive to antipsychotic treatment, supporting a functional contribution of GC deficits.

Further evidence comes from *Scn2a*^{+/-} mice, carrying mutations in a gene conferring risk across neurodevelopmental disorders including SZ. In this model, GCs display reduced intrinsic excitability and impaired high-frequency transmission, failing parallel fiber–Purkinje cell LTP while LTD remains intact (Wang, Derderian et al. 2024).

In contrast, **22q11.2** deletion models, including *Df(16)1/+* and *Tbx1*^{+/-} mice, show preserved GCs neurogenesis and baseline synaptic transmission, but selective disruption of parallel fiber–Purkinje cell plasticity, indicating circuit-level vulnerability in the absence of overt granule cell loss (Eom, Schmitt et al. 2024).

Finally, ataxic models harbouring mutations in *Grid2*, a SZ risk gene encoding the GluD2 receptor, exhibit granule cell depletion, defective pf–pc synapse formation, and abnormal cf innervation (Miyoshi, Yoshioka et al. 2014). Although these models are not SZ-specific, they highlight gene-dependent mechanisms through which GC dysfunction can alter cerebellar microcircuits.

Collectively, genetic animal models indicate that GC development, intrinsic excitability, and synaptic output are sensitive to SZ-associated genetic perturbations. While not all models show overt GC loss, convergent disruptions of mf–gc signalling and parallel fibre transmission suggest that GC dysfunction contributes to cerebellar circuit instability in SZ. These findings underscore gene-specific mechanisms that selectively affect GCs and shape cerebellar network output without uniform structural degeneration.

3.2.2 Pharmacological perturbation models affecting granule cell function

Pharmacological perturbation models have provided mechanistic insight into how dysregulation of neurotransmitter systems implicated in SZ impacts cerebellar GC function. Although these models do not recapitulate SZ as a neurodevelopmental disorder, they enable controlled interrogation of dopaminergic and glutamatergic influences on cerebellar input processing and microcircuit dynamics (See review (Faris, Pischedda et al. 2024)), highlighting how dysregulation in various neurotransmitter systems may contribute to the disorder. Among these, NMDAR antagonists, such as ketamine and PCP, induce structural and neurochemical changes in the cerebellum, specifically reduced PC density (see section 2.2.2) and disrupted neurotransmitter balance.

Psychostimulant exposure, including **methamphetamine** and amphetamine administration, produces robust alterations in cerebellar activity and connectivity. Acute methamphetamine treatment increases c-fos mRNA expression in GCs across anterior and posterior cerebellar lobules, reflecting heightened excitability mediated primarily by D1 receptor activation (Hamamura, Ozawa et al. 1999). With repeated exposure, this response attenuates, particularly in the anterior hemisphere and posterior vermis (lobule VII), indicating activity-dependent adaptation within GC populations. Notably, prolonged

methamphetamine exposure also delays GC migration, suggesting that sustained dopaminergic perturbation interferes with cerebellar developmental dynamics (Hamamura, Ozawa et al. 1999).

NMDA receptor antagonist models further implicate GC-centered circuit dysregulation. In the **PCP**-treated rat, reduced expression of GAD67, GAD65, and the GABA transporter GAT-1 in GoCs, coupled with compensatory changes in GABA(A) receptor subunits, is predicted to disinhibit GCs by weakening feedforward and feedback inhibition (Bullock, Bolognani et al. 2009). Additional compensatory mechanisms include downregulation of kainate receptor subunits and extrasynaptic NMDA receptor components, indicating complex adaptive responses within the granule cell–Golgi cell network (Bullock, Cardon et al. 2008, Bullock, Bolognani et al. 2009). These alterations parallel aspects of inhibitory–excitatory imbalance reported in SZ, although their direction and magnitude differ between pharmacological models and human tissue. Ketamine exposure also induces cerebellar histoarchitectural disruption, although layer-specific effects on GCs remain less well delineated (Omeiza, Bakre et al. 2023). Together, these pharmacological studies demonstrate that GC excitability, migration, and inhibitory control are highly sensitive to SZ-relevant neurotransmitter perturbations.

Collectively, pharmacological perturbation models indicate that cerebellar GC activity and inhibitory regulation are vulnerable to dopaminergic and glutamatergic dysregulation. Although these findings do not establish disease specificity, they reveal convergent mechanisms through which altered neurotransmission may destabilize cerebellar input layers and contribute to circuit-level dysfunction relevant to SZ.

3.2.3 Neurodevelopmental risk models affecting granule cells

Neurodevelopmental risk models based on maternal infection, early-life stress, and prenatal toxic exposure provide etiologically relevant insight into how environmental insults disrupt GC development during critical periods of cerebellar maturation. Epidemiological data link maternal immune activation and early stress to increased risk of psychosis, and corresponding animal models reproduce persistent cerebellar alterations without modelling SZ as a diagnostic entity (Fineberg, Ellman et al. 2016, Egorova, Egorov et al. 2024).

Maternal immune activation models, including poly (I:C) and influenza exposure, induce region-specific cerebellar abnormalities in offspring. In these models, GC development is disrupted early, with abnormal expansion of the external granule layer during embryogenesis, particularly in lobules VI and VII, followed by long-lasting alterations in granule cell organization (Shi, Smith et al. 2009), occur alongside PC deficits. Early-life stress paradigms further demonstrate GC sensitivity to environmental perturbation. For instance, a rodent study examining **maternal separation** for 180 minutes (MS180) during early postnatal development found increased GrC survival and integration into adult cerebellar circuits (Roque, Lajud et al. 2019). Immediate increases in GrC survival at postnatal day fifteen were observed, and the persistent effects extended into adulthood, P60. This persistent neurogenic response,

combined with elevated adult corticosterone levels, suggests that early stress exposure contributes to SZ-relevant cerebellar changes by modulating GrC development.

The **MAM** model provides extensive evidence that prenatal disruption of neurogenesis profoundly affects GC populations. MAM exposure at embryonic or early postnatal stages induces apoptosis of GC precursors, reduces granule cell density, disrupts migration from the external to the internal granule layer, and leads to hypogranular cerebella (Ferrer, Pozas et al. 1997, Ferrer, Puig et al. 2001). These structural alterations are accompanied by reduced synaptic density, impaired synaptophysin expression, and persistent changes in glutamatergic receptor signaling, including upregulation of group I metabotropic glutamate receptors and delayed maturation of group II receptors (Becker, Gombos et al. 1996, Ulupinar and Yucel 2005). Disrupted CG development in this model secondarily alters PC organization and cerebellar foliation, underscoring the interdependence of cerebellar cortical layers.

Together, neurodevelopmental risk models demonstrate that GCs are highly sensitive to early-life immune, stress-related, and toxic insults during cerebellar development. Although these models do not establish SZ-specific pathology, they reveal convergent mechanisms through which disrupted GC proliferation, migration, and synaptic integration can produce long-lasting cerebellar circuit abnormalities. These findings support a developmental vulnerability framework in which early environmental factors shape cerebellar dysfunction relevant to SZ.

Figure 3. Granule cell alterations in SZ: summary of evidence from human postmortem and SZ-relevant animal model studies.

4. Inhibitory interneurons and glial alterations in SZ

Cerebellar inhibitory interneurons play a vital role in ensuring the proper timing and integration of neuronal activity. These interneurons, encompassing GoCs, BCs, and SCs, are GABAergic and provide feedback and feedforward inhibition to GrCs and PCs. GoCs exert lateral inhibition on GrCs, shaping the cerebellar input stage. BC and SC provide additional control by inhibiting PCs and regulating the overall E/I balance in the cerebellar circuits (D'Angelo, Solinas et al. 2013, Kim and Augustine 2021). The dysfunction of these inhibitory interneurons might disrupt overall cerebellar neuronal excitability, contributing to various neurological and psychiatric disorders, including SZ, where altered GABAergic signalling has been implicated (See review (Faris, Pischetta et al. 2024)). Here, we explore how changes in these cell types of manifest in SZ through a detailed examination of findings from clinical, postmortem, and animal model studies (**Figure 3**).

GoCs inhibit GrCs through their extensive axonal arborization and by forming synapses with multiple glomeruli. On one hand, this inhibitory control is critical for the precise timing and integration of GrC activity, influencing cerebellar output and overall cerebellar function, as it generates a broad lateral inhibition extending beyond the afferent synaptic field. On the other hand, GoCs receive a double excitatory input, mf on the basal dendrites and pf on the apical dendrites and play a key role in feedback inhibition within the cerebellar circuitry (Galliano, Mazzarello et al. 2010, D'Angelo, Solinas et al. 2013).

Postmortem studies indicate selective impairment of GoC-associated inhibitory markers in SZ. Reduced expression of GABA-synthesizing enzymes, including GAD67 and GAD65, as well as the GABA transporter GAT-1, has been reported in the cerebellum of individuals with SZ (Bullock, Cardon et al. 2008, Yeganeh-Doost, Gruber et al. 2011). In addition, decreased expression of mGluR2 and nNOS in GoCs suggests impaired modulation of inhibitory transmission. Together, these changes predict weakened phasic inhibition of GrCs, potentially leading to GC disinhibition and altered downstream PC output. Such disruption may compromise information flow through cortico–cerebellar–thalamo–cortical circuits implicated in cognitive dysfunction.

Pharmacological perturbation models support this interpretation. Chronic low-dose PCP treatment in rats selectively disrupts GoC function, reducing mRNA levels of GAD67, GAD65, and GAT-1 while inducing compensatory upregulation of extrasynaptic GABA_A receptor subunits ($\alpha 6$, $\beta 3$, δ) (Bullock, Bolognani et al. 2009). NMDA receptor subunits preferentially expressed in GoCs (NR2B and NR2D) are reduced, whereas other subunits remain unchanged, indicating cell-type-specific vulnerability. Functional recordings show reduced GoC pacemaker firing, consistent with impaired inhibitory control over GrCs. Notably, these changes are selective for GoCs, with basket cells, stellate cells, and PCs largely spared, underscoring a targeted disruption of the cerebellar input stage.

Clinical and preclinical studies further implicate parvalbumin-positive interneurons in cerebellar dysfunction. Reduced stability of perineuronal nets and altered calcium-binding protein expression have been reported in SZ, suggesting compromised structural support for fast-spiking interneurons (Berretta, Pantazopoulos et al. 2015, Vidal-Domènech, Riquelme et al. 2020). Although most evidence in SZ concerns cortical PV-positive interneurons, these findings highlight mechanisms that can impair transmission fidelity and network synchronisation. Because parvalbumin-expressing basket and stellate cells regulate the temporal precision of PC firing, similar disturbances could disrupt cerebellar inhibitory control and contribute to cognitive dysfunction (Gonzalez-Burgos, Fish et al. 2011, Stedehouder and Kushner 2017). GoCs and PV+ interneuron population reductions disrupt inhibitory control within cerebellar circuits. Loss or dysfunction of these interneuron populations reduces inhibitory regulation of granule cell activity and alters the balance of excitation reaching PC, a phenomenon observed in both SZ models and clinical samples, underscoring a convergence of cellular and synaptic dysfunctions that impair the cerebellar contribution to higher cognitive functions in SZ (Faris, Pischedda et al. 2024).

Glial cells, particularly Bergmann glia and microglia, contribute critically to cerebellar development, synaptic maintenance, and injury response. In neurodevelopmental models, including MAM exposure, Bergmann glia exhibits reactive changes marked by increased GFAP and vimentin expression, thickened processes, and phagocytic activity surrounding apoptotic granule cell precursors (Lafarga, Andres et al. 1998). Ultrastructural studies reveal active clearance of apoptotic debris by both Bergmann glia and amoeboid microglia, highlighting coordinated glial responses to developmental injury.

Additional studies report transient shortening and disorganization of Bergmann glial radial fibers following MAM exposure, accompanied by loss of basket cells and disrupted cerebellar cytoarchitecture (de Barry, Gombos et al. 1987, Luthman, Eriksson-Nilsson et al. 1990). Because Bergmann glia provides structural and trophic support for PC dendritic development and migration, their displacement is likely to exacerbate neuronal disorganization. These glial alterations occur alongside GC displacement into the molecular layer and abnormal PC positioning, emphasizing the interdependence of neuronal and glial integrity during cerebellar development (Yamanaka and Obata 2004). Additionally, microglia have been implicated in cerebellar alterations in SZ-relevant models. In a 2HIT paradigm combining maternal infection and repeated social defeat stress, inflammatory insults produced a marked increase in cerebellar microglia that correlated with PC loss. Microglia shifted toward a TREM2-positive stress-associated phenotype linked to IL-6 and TGF β signalling. These changes were accompanied by reduced PC excitability, cerebellar network dysconnectivity, and behavioural abnormalities (Hikosaka, Parvez et al. 2025).

Together, evidence from human studies and experimental models indicates that dysfunction of inhibitory interneurons and glial cells destabilizes E/I balance within cerebellar circuits. Impaired Golgi

cell inhibition altered PV+ interneuron function, and maladaptive glial responses converge to disrupt the timing and precision of cerebellar processing. These alterations are expected to impair cerebellar contributions to prediction, coordination, and cognitive integration, providing a mechanistic link between microcircuit dysfunction and the cognitive and perceptual disturbances observed in SZ.

Figure 4. Interneuron alterations in SZ

5. Conclusions

5.1 Cellular alterations in the human cerebellum in SZ

Several papers report a reduction of cerebellar volume and alterations in cellular organization in subjects diagnosed with SZ (**Figures 1-4**). Tashiro reported cerebellar atrophy related to a reduced PC number (Tashiro, Suzuki et al. 1999). Slater and Mavroudis reported reduced ML thickness, in the latter case related to PC dendritic arborization (Slater, Doyle et al. 1998, Mavroudis, Petrides et al. 2017). Eom, in a familiar SZ subgroup (22q11.2DS) reported a decrease in cerebellar volume (Eom, Schmitt et al. 2024). In aggregate, these observations point to a reduction in cerebellar volume (at least in certain regions) correlated with alterations in the molecular layer, specifically targeting the PC dendrites. The absence of PC linear density reduction (Tran, Smutzer et al. 1998, Lingärde, Jönsson et al. 2000, Mavroudis, Petrides et al. 2017) may indicate that the PCs linear density is largely preserved, despite relevant alterations in the dendrites and, consequently, in ML thickness and cerebellar volume. The cellular alterations have not been studied in depth but point to a reduction of PC dendritic complexity, including lower branch number, density, and length, bringing about a lower number of synaptic contacts (Mavroudis, Petrides et al. 2017). Sparse data report several functional alterations potentially affecting the glutamatergic system and the E/I balance (Bernstein, Krell et al. 2001, Yao, Zhao et al. 2025), reduction of D-serine and disrupted glutamatergic neurotransmission (Ono, Shishido et al. 2009). It

should be noted that D-serine is an NMDARs co-agonist, and that NOS is activated by calcium influx through NMDARs, suggesting that the glutamatergic hypothesis of SZ (Bernstein, Krell et al. 2001, Uzun Uysal, Tomruk et al. 2024) applies to the cerebellar as well as to other brain circuits. Given the prevalent localization of glutamatergic and NMDA-dependent mechanisms in the granular layer, it is quite likely that it is involved in determining alterations in the SZ cerebellum, although this aspect has not received enough attention so far.

5.2 Cellular alterations in the rodent cerebellum relevant to SZ

There are numerous studies on animal models reproducing the SZ pathology in rodents, which report a reduction of volume and alterations in the cellular organization (**Figures 1-4**) of the cerebellum. These animal models provided details about the nature of alterations and the pathogenetic mechanisms. Genetic, pharmacological, and maternal-stress models consistently reported cerebellar atrophy associated with reduced molecular layer thickness, reduced PC number, and alterations in PC soma, dendrites, and axons. Dendritic alterations include reduced soma size and dendritic arborization, orientation, complexity, length, and branching. Along with this, there is a reduction in spine density and synaptic connectivity (Hartkop and Jones 1977, Zuo, De Jager et al. 1997, Hamamura, Watanabe et al. 2004, Maloku, Covelo et al. 2010, Pascual, Ebner et al. 2010, Kim, Kwon et al. 2011, Miyoshi, Yoshioka et al. 2014, Tian, Tep et al. 2014, Pascual, Valencia et al. 2015, Mugikura, Katoh et al. 2016, Shevelkin, Terrillion et al. 2017, Dong, Mao et al. 2021, Tapias, Lázaro et al. 2021, Hwang, Kim et al. 2022, Veleanu, Urrieta-Chávez et al. 2022, Omeiza, Bakre et al. 2023, Schmitt, DeBevits et al. 2023, Xu, Wang et al. 2023, Eom, Schmitt et al. 2024, Wang, Derderian et al. 2024, Hikosaka, Parvez et al. 2025). These observations are consistent with postmortem findings in humans. Animal models also provided evidence for the functional changes that occur in the cerebellar circuit, although, in general, it is hard to disentangle pathogenic from compensatory changes. Conversely, PCs in *Disc1* mice showed increased intrinsic excitability, spontaneous firing, and EPSCs, suggesting that the granular layer is transmitting more intense signals and that PCs are more reactive to the inputs, supporting the existence of compensatory mechanisms (Shevelkin, Terrillion et al. 2017). In 22q11DS mice, pf-PC LTD is specifically impaired (Eom, Schmitt et al. 2024). PCP data imply that a reduced NMDAR-dependent transmission could be implicated along with alterations of synaptic inhibition provided by the inhibitory circuits formed by Golgi cells and molecular layer interneurons (Bullock, Cardon et al. 2008, Bullock, Bolognani et al. 2009). MAM data also imply a reduced number of granule cells. Therefore, the focus moves to the granular layer and its powerful NMDAR-dependent system.

5.3 A general hypothesis of cerebellar neuronal alterations in SZ

The emerging picture is that the SZ cerebellum presents relevant changes, suggesting the combination of pathogenic alterations and compensatory mechanisms that develop along the course of ontogenesis (Mitoma, Buffo et al. 2020, Udeh-Momoh, Migeot et al. 2025). Rather than isolated alterations, these

changes affect the cerebellar network at multiple levels, involving Purkinje cells, granule cells, and inhibitory interneurons.

The cerebellar changes have been mostly studied in PCs (see section 2), which show reduction of the dendritic tree and impairment in several excitable and synaptic mechanisms. However, relevant changes emerged both in the molecular and granular layers, involving all the main cerebellar neurons. Therefore, SZ shows a global change in the cerebellar network, of which PC alterations are just a part.

Available data support the hypothesis of E/I imbalance, with hypofunctioning of the NMDARs-dependent system and various alterations in the GABAergic system, both in the granular and molecular layer. Given the prominent expression of NMDARs in the granular layer, this latter is likely to play a much deeper role in SZ than previously thought. Alterations in NMDA and GABA-A receptor subunits seem to specifically target the granular layer through a wrong neurodevelopmental process, altering synapse formation, NMDARs trafficking, neurotransmitter release, and related homeostatic processes. A deficit in NR2B expression would alter the development of the mf-GC relay, while at later stages, NR2A and NR2C expression would remain unaltered (Bullock, Cardon et al. 2008). Among other possible alterations are those concerning the inhibitory loops provided by GOs, which indeed show altered GABA-A release and postsynaptic receptor expression. These cerebellar granular layer alterations could bring about a deficit in multimodal fusion, which is a hallmark of SZ. It should be noted that NR2B receptor subunits continue to be expressed in the adult cerebellum in GOs and molecular layer interneurons, so that the alterations could be perpetuated in some parts of the circuit. NMDARs are critical, along with the inhibitory loops controlling their voltage-dependent unblock, for the generation of long-term synaptic plasticity and circuit computation. Such alterations may constitute a central mechanism underlying cerebellar dysfunction in SZ. Alterations in the molecular layer could be either a consequence of altered granular signal transmission or develop in parallel and (at least partly) independently, adding further complexity to the pathology.

Within a predictive processing framework, these alterations can be interpreted as impairments in the generation and updating of internal models. Granule cell dysfunction may degrade input encoding and context integration, while abnormal Purkinje cell output may impair prediction error signaling and its transmission to thalamo-cortical circuits. This combined disruption provides a mechanistic basis for deficits in cognitive coordination, sensory integration, and adaptive behaviour observed in SZ.

Another aspect that merits attention is the role of the cerebellar dopaminergic system, which was previously suggested as a possible important component of SZ physiopathology (Faris, Pischedda et al. 2024). There are no clear indications about cellular alterations implying its involvement in SZ. However, we noticed that the cerebellum has a triple relationship with the dopaminergic system: it produces dopamine, it receives dopaminergic innervation, and it regulates the dopaminergic systems of the brain stem and basal ganglia. Since PCs in SZ are hypoplastic, the cerebellar production of dopamine may be

reduced (as it also occurs in Parkinson's disease), see Gambosi et al., 2023 (Gambosi, Sheiban et al. 2023). Alterations in the cerebellar circuit would impair the control of dopamine release from the VTA. Finally, D1 and D2 receptors can upregulate or downregulate NMDARs' functions via cAMP level control (Snyder, Fienberg et al. 1998, Wang, Wong et al. 2012). Therefore, dopaminergic drugs would eventually impact the NMDARs-dependent control of cerebellar activity.

Overall, we propose that cerebellar dysfunction in SZ arises from the combined impairment of granule cell input processing and Purkinje cell output, leading to disrupted predictive computation and large-scale network dyscoordination. This framework links cellular alterations to the cognitive and perceptual disturbances characteristic of the disorder and provides a basis for future experimental and computational investigations.

5.4 Open questions

Despite converging evidence for cerebellar involvement in SZ, several key questions remain unresolved and limit the translation of cellular findings into mechanistic understanding.

1. A central issue concerns the causal role/ contribution of cerebellar pathology. It remains unclear whether cellular alterations in PCs and granule cells represent primary pathogenic mechanisms or arise secondarily from early disturbances in cortical or subcortical systems. Resolving this question is essential to determine whether the cerebellum acts as a driver or a downstream node within distributed disease networks.
2. The temporal emergence of cerebellar alterations is also poorly defined. Current evidence, largely derived from chronic postmortem samples, does not clarify whether these changes originate during neurodevelopment, evolve progressively across disease stages, or reflect stable trait-like abnormalities. Longitudinal and early-stage studies are required to map the developmental trajectory of cerebellar dysfunction.
3. A major gap concerns the link between cellular alterations and cognitive dysfunction. While cerebellar abnormalities are consistently associated with cognitive deficits, direct evidence connecting specific cellular phenotypes to impairments in prediction, working memory, or executive function remains limited. Establishing these relationships is critical to validate cerebellar dysfunction as a mechanistic substrate of cognitive symptoms.
4. Another unresolved question involves the structure–function relationship. It remains unclear whether morphological alterations in cerebellar neurons directly drive functional abnormalities, such as disrupted excitatory–inhibitory balance and impaired predictive computation, or whether functional dysregulation precedes and shapes structural changes.
5. The issue of disease specificity also remains open. Many cerebellar alterations overlap with findings in other psychiatric conditions, particularly with bipolar (Maloku, Covelo et al. 2010) and neurodevelopmental disorders like Autism, raising the question of whether SZ is

characterized by distinct cerebellar cellular signatures or by shared transdiagnostic mechanisms.

6. The relative contribution of genetic and environmental factors to cerebellar pathology is insufficiently understood. Although genetic risk, neurodevelopmental insults, and environmental exposures likely converge on cerebellar circuits, their interaction at the cellular level remains largely unexplored.
7. Finally, the therapeutic relevance of cerebellar dysfunction is still emerging. While neuromodulatory approaches targeting cerebellar circuits show promise (Hua, Abram et al. 2022), the cellular mechanisms underlying treatment response and their impact on predictive processing and cognition remain unclear.
8. Direct experimental evidence linking cerebellar cellular alterations to predictive processing deficits in psychosis remains lacking
9. Heterogeneity across patients suggests that cerebellar involvement may define specific psychosis subtypes rather than a uniform mechanism

Addressing these challenges will require integrative approaches combining longitudinal human studies, cell-type-specific postmortem analyses, advanced animal models, and multiscale computational frameworks (D'Angelo and Jirsa 2022, De Schepper, Geminiani et al. 2022) and digital cerebellum models embedding SZ-like features (Vergani et al. 2026), capable of linking cellular alterations to circuit dynamics and behaviour.

6. Author contributions

PF: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. AAV: Writing – review & editing. IH: Writing – review & editing. SM: Writing – reviewing & editing. PFP: Reviewing & editing. ED'A: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

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